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Co-author(s):	L. Ramos (DERLab), P. Karafotis (HEDNO), A. Kontou (ICCS), E. Widl, T. Strasser (AIT)
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List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CPES	Cyber-Physical Energy Systems
CHIL	Control Hardware-in-the-Loop
DC	Direct Current
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DG	Distributed Generation
DoA	Description of Action
DRTS	Digital Real-Time Simulator
DUT	Device Under Test
EES-UETP	Electric Energy Systems University Enterprise Training Partnership
ERA-Net	European Research Area Network
ERN	European Researcher's Night
ESS	Energy Storage System
FS	Functional Scenario
GA	Grant Agreement
GDRTS	Geographically Distributed Real-Time Simulation
GDHIL	Geographically Distributed Hardware-in-the-Loop
GP	General Public
H2020	Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Framework Program
HIL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
HW	Hardware
HSS	High School Student
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IEA	International Energy Agency
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
ILO	Intended Learning Outcome
ISGAN	International Smart Grid Action Network
JRA	Joint Research Activity
NA	Networking Activity
P	Professionals
PELS	Power Electronics Society
PES	Power and Energy Society
PHIL	Power Hardware-in-the-Loop
PhD	Doctor of Philosophy
PV	Photovoltaic
RES	Renewable Energy System
RI	Research Infrastructure
SES	Smart Energy Systems
SIRFN	Smart Grid International Research Facility Network
TCP	Technology Cooperation Program
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

Executive Summary

ERIGrid 2.0 training and educational activities aim to inform a broad audience about best practices and latest advancement in methods, approaches and tools for the development, validation and roll-out of smart energy systems solutions.

This report revisits the *educational strategy* of the project. The educational strategy has been developed as a methodology for educational program management, offering a tool for coordination and alignment of the training activities. The methodology is described and applied, combining qualitative and quantitative top-down feedback for the bottom-up decentralised organisation of training activities. This feedback supports the alignment of training activities concerning scope, activity type, and target audiences along the project lifecycle.

The educational strategy analysis finds that, in contrast with the previous educational strategy analysis, now all intended target groups, intended training activity types, and research areas have been covered. Also, the previously considered low competence level among the intended learning outcomes has been adjusted to cover the full spectrum of competence levels.

The *on-site training activities* reported span a wide range of training events, including training for high-school students, the general public as well as industry professionals and researchers. The training activities span a good range and number: Four training schools for PhD students and researchers were planned, of which two physical schools have been implemented and one was implemented as a multi-day online training event; the fourth event is planned to be hosted in March 2025. Four events were hosted for high schools and the general public, and one event was hosted for the training of professionals. Ten workshops were organized and hosted by the project partners, each attracting between seven and 50 participants, attracting a total of 340 researchers and professionals. At international conferences, five panel sessions were organised and four tutorials were given. In summary, the performed and planned training activities fulfilled and exceeded the intended project objectives.

The *staff exchange* reports on an internal program for training and collaboration between partners, with a focus on the exchange of experiences and expertise. For the past 22 months, five additional staff exchanges have been reported, summing to a total of 17 staff exchanges in the project period. The reduced number compared to the previous report, (*D-NA3.1a Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges, 2023*), is also a result of the conclusion of joint research activities in ERIGrid 2.0.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

ERIGrid 2.0 training and educational activities aim to inform a broad audience about best practices and latest advancement in methods, approaches and tools for the development, validation and roll-out of smart energy system solutions. The project ambition is to apply state of the art teaching approaches and techniques, such as active and student-driven learning, self-study, and digital learning platforms. The training content can be adapted to various audiences.

This document provides a final update of Deliverable D4.1 (*D-NA3.1a Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges, 2023*), reporting on three areas of training related activities: the educational strategy, all on-site physical training activities carried out, and the ERIGrid 2.0 internal staff exchange.

The *educational strategy* aims to provide a qualitative and quantitative reflection on the areas of training developed in the project. Utilising surveys and systematic reporting, an overview of the topical areas developed in the project is documented. The templates and forms developed in the educational strategy offer a common structure for feedback and the future improvement of training.

The *on-site training activities* reported in this document span a wide range of training events, including training for high-school students, the general public as well as industry professionals and researchers.

The *staff exchange* reports on an internal programme for training and collaboration across partners, where the exchange of experience and expertise is in focus.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 2 describes the revisited educational strategy approach and presents an updated summary of training activity progress concerning the strategic training goals. Section 3 lists all executed on-site training activities and provides summaries for the training activities executed since the last report. Section 4 describes the structure and results of the staff exchange programme since the previous report. The deliverable is concluded in Section 5. Finally, additional content is provided in the Appendix A and Appendix B, where a publication, the original templates, activity plans, activity reports, and staff exchange reports are included.

2 Educational Strategy

This section presents a progress update regarding the Educational Strategy applied in the ERIGrid 2.0 project. Updates to the methodology and project progress are presented relative to the initial iteration of this deliverable, i.e., Deliverable D4.1.

2.1 Overview and Updates

The educational strategy methodology and its application in ERIGrid 2.0 was first outlined in Deliverable D4.1, and further detailed in (Kontou et al., 2024).

As defined previously, the *Educational Strategy*

“[A]ims to provide orientation and coordination of the ERIGrid 2.0 educational activities. The concept behind this approach is to assemble bottom-up developed educational elements such as surveys, training objectives and learning modules, and to develop a coherent picture of these inputs. The educational strategy is based on an analysis of training content in the form of stated training objectives and intended learning outcomes, and aims to contrast content of already the delivered training activities with the planned and intended training activities. The result informs a gap analysis, recognising the areas where the project can focus additional efforts to realise the intended training outcomes.” (D-NA3.1a Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges, 2023)

This report aims to revisit the results of adjustment undertaken since the gap analysis from the previous deliverable, and the overall progress of the project in the field of the intended training activities. As a basis for this reflection serves a comparison of the measured progress achieved since the first report iteration.

Therefore, the following sections follow the same structure as introduced in Deliverable D4.1. Since no additional adjustment is possible due to the imminent finalisation of the project, the initial survey results are not repeated here.

As the comparison in the following sections will reveal, all intended areas have been addressed - the number of activities and the topic coverage now represents the full spectrum intended, all planned target groups have been addressed, and all intended types of validation methods were included. The lagging behind of face-to-face activities in the previous report has been more than caught up. Considering the balance of topics addressed, measured in “Functional Scenarios” (*D-NA4.1 Functional Scenarios, 2020*) as integrated clusters, and by “Research topics” as identified through the initial survey, we find that common trends have emerged. For example, the former digital lead topics such as “Demand response” and “Aggregation and Flexibility Management” are less in focus today than expected, and the previously reported trend in support of the Functional Scenario “Digitalisation” and sister topic “Digitalisation in Energy Systems” have persisted to dominate.

Overall, the project achieved a balanced progress, met all the intended project goals, and even exceeded most of them.

2.2 Educational Strategy – Methodology Update

The educational strategy method has been refined since the previous report, even though the main concepts remain the same. The paper (Kontou et al., 2024) is also included in this report as Appendix A.1.

The core idea remains as outlined previously, but a few adjustments have been formulated. In particular, the overall process and role of different forms and documents has been clarified, as illustrated in Figure 1. Four main steps are, as performed in ERIGrid 2.0: (1) activity topic scoping jointly with all partners, (2) activity planning (bottom up, including the formulation of Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs) for relevant activities), (3) activity reporting and feedback collection, the (4) formulation of an educational strategy to consolidate the achieved results with the project ambitions, generating a feedback-based top down steering effect. Here, steps (2) and (3) occur continuously along with training activity implementation. The intention for this methodology is to perform the above steps (2)-(4) cyclically, at a rate matching the steering need observed in the project.

Figure 1: Overview of Methodology, from (Kontou et al., 2024).

Another key contribution of the conference paper in Appendix A.1 is the contextualisation of the ERIGrid 2.0 educational strategy approach in educational programme management, contrasting classical educational programmes with the management of training needs in large, distributed research projects such as ERIGrid 2.0. Emphasis is placed on the need to accommodate a bottom-up approach in the formulation and execution of training activities, and an iterative top-down evaluation and strategy alignment based on programme objectives. The analysis of bottom-up provided ILOs using Bloom's Taxonomy ("Bloom's taxonomy: Original and revised", 2005), here presented in its revised version, remains central to the interpretation and alignment feedback generated from the educational strategy.

2.3 Update on Types of Training Activities and Intended Target Groups

This section introduces all the types of training activities considered in ERIGrid 2.0, and compares the planned and reported number of activities in each category.

2.3.1 Training Activity Types

The training activities revisited in this section are considering both the physical on-site training sessions and the online training offers. Types of educational activities associated with a physical location are further reported on in Section 3. The activity categories are defined as follows (cf. (*D-NA3.1a Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges, 2023*) for definitions):

1. *Training Schools*
2. *Training of High School Students*
3. *Training of Professionals*
4. *Workshops and Seminars*
5. *Special and Panel Sessions*
6. *Tutorials*

Purely digital training resources and activities are reported in Deliverable D4.3 (*D-NA3.2 Education and Training Material for E-learning and Laboratory Education, 2023*) and D4.4 (*D-NA3.3 Lessons Learned and Recommendations for Laboratory Education and E-learning Tools, 2025*), however, they are reflected in the educational strategy as well. The list of training activity types is as follows (refer to (*D-NA3.1a Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges, 2023*) for definitions):

1. *Webinars*
2. *Education Tools*
3. *Interactive Notebooks*
4. *Virtual Laboratories*
5. *Remote Laboratories*
6. *Videos*
7. *Co-simulation Education*
8. *Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) Education*
9. *Hardware (HW) Setups Education*

Mode of Training Activity Execution

An additional classifier field quantifies how the activity is held, i.e., whether the activity was virtual, face-to-face or material disseminated as open access to the public.

Analysis of Activity Plans

In the past release of this deliverable, the number of activities held face-to-face was ragged compared to the virtual training activities. Once the results were updated, it can be observed that, beyond the initial predictions, there was a huge increase in the Face-to-Face events, while more online events were also organised, thus keeping the balance. The summary of the analysis in the previous release of this deliverable and this final release is shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3.

Figure 2: Analysis of other classifiers covered by ERIGrid 2.0 project's training activities delivered and in planning by March 2023.

Figure 3: Analysis of other classifiers covered by ERIGrid 2.0 project's training activities delivered and in planning up to date.

The training activities considered in the educational strategy analysis encompass all of the listed training activities. In the previous release, the results indicated that ERIGrid 2.0 training activities already covered all three aforementioned formats. In the past, the predominant format was online whereas presently, the Face-to-Face predominates, accounting for a total of 23 delivered activities and 2 under planning. Subsequently, it follows the online format accounting for 18 delivered and 3 activities under planning. Lastly, it closes the open access material with 6 delivered and 2 under planning associated activities. By comparing both figures, it can be seen a balance in the number of activities online and Face-to-Face was achieved as more activities were organised.

2.3.2 Target Groups

ERIGrid 2.0 aims to reach a broad audience, so it involves several target groups in the training activities that are carried out. The main target groups are listed below (definitions in (*D-NA3.1a Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges, 2023*)):

1. *Young Researchers – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) Students*
2. *Undergraduate Students*
3. *Power System Professionals*
4. *Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) Professionals*
5. *High School Students*

Analysis of Activity Plans

Figure 4 and Figure 5 show the distribution of the activities according to the target groups established at the beginning of the project from both the previous release of this deliverable and this final release, respectively. Note that, depending on its scope, a single activity may cover multiple groups.

Figure 4: Analysis of target groups covered by ERIGrid 2.0 project's training activities delivered and in planning by March 2023.

Figure 5: Analysis of target groups covered by ERIGrid 2.0 project's training activities delivered and in planning up to date.

Overall, the results show that the trend concerning the first release analysis remains. Thus, both young researchers and professionals stand for the main target groups in the training activities, followed by undergraduate students. In contrast, there were no additional activities organised for high school students. From the training activities already delivered and in planning status up to date, 41 involved power system professionals, 37 targeted young researchers, 29 were oriented to undergraduate students, 21 implicated ICT professionals, and 3 involved high school students. Therefore, all intended target groups have gained benefit from the training activities by ERIGrid 2.0.

2.4 Analysis of Training Activity Scope and Objectives

To set the ambition and to enable a quantitative analysis of the training activity scope, the project defined several classifiers for training activity topics. Considering the scope of ERIGrid 2.0, technical topics are viewed from both a *technology application* point of view and the perspective of *testing and validation methods*. Also, the project defined a set of six “*Functional Scenarios (FSs)*” at the outset in Deliverable D5.1 (*D-NA4.1 Functional Scenarios*, 2020). These three points of view define the technical areas in which all training activities of ERIGrid 2.0 should be classified. The areas will only be listed in the following, but have been defined in more detail in (*D-NA3.1a Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges*, 2023).

2.4.1 Functional Scenarios

To specify the project ambition, at the outset of the project, the partners formulated several FS, each of which combined under a coherent theme, stakeholders, technical and business areas, with related use case and test cases (*D-NA4.1 Functional Scenarios, 2020*):

1. *FS1 - Ancillary Services Provided by Distributed Energy Resource (DER)s and Active Grid Assets*
2. *FS2 - Microgrids and Energy Community*
3. *FS3 - Sector Coupling*
4. *FS4 - Frequency and Voltage Stability in Inverter Dominated Power Systems*
5. *FS5 - Aggregation and Flexibility Management*
6. *FS6 - Digitalisation*

Analysis of Activity Plans

In the quantification of the FSs covered by the training activities it was found that the trend concerning the previous release of this deliverable remains. Thus, most of the activities are classified within the FS6 as shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7. Digitalisation thus remains the most popular topic among the activities organised in ERIGrid 2.0. For the case of FS5 and FS4, only a few training activities have been classified under these FSs. This may be explained by the fact that, for instance, only a few activities have been organised on the topic of flexibility management or frequency and voltage stability. Moreover, in this release one activity organised covered the FS5 which had not been covered in the past.

Figure 6: Analysis of Functional Scenarios covered by ERIGrid 2.0 project's training activities delivered and in planning by March 2023.

Figure 7: Analysis of Functional Scenarios covered by ERIGrid 2.0 project's training activities delivered and in planning up to date.

In summary, for this release, the statistics show that eight activities were organised for FS1, the same amount for FS2, four activities for FS3, and two activities for FS4. For FS5 only one

activity was organised, while the highest number of activities can be counted in FS6 with 31 activities. Note that an activity may belong to more than one FS.

2.4.2 Training Activity Topics and Focus Areas

The area of subjects covered by ERIGrid 2.0 is quite broad, so that it was helpful to break down the topics into more concrete areas of work. This classification was performed early in the project, in the context of an internal survey. The topics were defined in (*D-NA3.1a Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges*, 2023), where also the internal survey results were reported. Since the topic list and survey had been defined before the functional scenarios had been developed, there are overlaps between these classifications. Since the definitions of the topics were included in (*D-NA3.1a Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges*, 2023), they are listed here:

1. *Distributed Energy Resources (DERs)*
2. *Energy Storage Systems (ESSs)*
3. *Distribution Management Systems and Distribution Network Operation*
4. *Ancillary Services by Distributed Generation (DG), Storage and Active Grid Assets*
5. *Frequency and Voltage Stability*
6. *Microgrids*
7. *Multi-energy/carrier systems/sector coupling*
8. *Inverter Dominated Power Systems*
9. *ICT in Smart Grids*
10. *Demand Response*
11. *Aggregation and Flexibility Management*
12. *Energy communities*
13. *Digitalisation of Energy Systems*
14. *Direct Current (DC) Power Systems*
15. *Energy Market*
16. *Other*

The above topics were explicitly inquired in the first survey. In the context of the activity plans, the mapping to the topics was done manually, based on the training activity description and training objectives.

Analysis of Activity Plans

The activity plans included in this analysis are embracing those already delivered or in planning status. It must be pointed out that the quantitative analysis is based on a qualitative (manual) interpretation of the reported activity plans.

The analysis gives insights on which topics from those initially listed in Section 2.3 were trending and which ones were vaguely covered, while comparing with the statistics from the previous

release of this deliverable (March 2023). That being said, Figure 8 and Figure 9 are illustrating the results of the topics analysis for both the delivered and in planning training activities from the previous release of this deliverable and this final release respectively. Note that, as in the first analysis, the sum of activities is higher than the actual number of delivered and in planning ones since a single activity may cover different topics on its scope.

Figure 8: Analysis of topics covered by ERIGrid 2.0 project's training activities delivered and in planning by March 2023.

Figure 9: Analysis of topics covered by ERIGrid 2.0 project's training activities delivered and in planning up to date.

The results are indicating that the most frequently represented topics remain the same, with *Distributed Energy Resources*, *ICT* and *Digitalisation of Energy Systems*. Each of these two topics was covered by more than ten activities, which sum up around half of the activities delivered. The other topics from the list are not appearing to the same extent. Moreover, the four

topics from the list which were not covered in the past release of the deliverable (*Inverter Dominated Power Systems, Demand Response, Aggregation and Flexibility Management, Energy Markets*) have been now successfully covered with at least one activity.

2.4.3 Validation Methods

The following list of research tools and laboratory testbeds is interpreted as an escalation of validation methods that can assist in maturing technologies to a range of Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs)¹. The methods considered here allow a validation of the range between TRL3 and TRL6, in exceptional cases even TRL7. The definitions were introduced in (*D-NA3.1a Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges, 2023*), but are repeated here for easier readability and minor refinements:

1. *Simulation (Monolithic)*: Monolithic simulation allows validation of algorithms, e.g., against a benchmark simulation model, achieving a maturity of typically TRL3.
2. *Co-simulation*: The co-simulation tools enable the joint simulation of different domains, e.g., electricity system together with communication network or the coupling of standalone simulators of different time steps, for the performance of a joint simulation.
3. *Control Hardware-in-the-Loop (CHIL)/Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL)*: HIL is an advanced laboratory testing method in which actual hardware components are interfaced to a Digital Real-Time Simulator (DRTS) for studying the behaviour of the Device Under Test (DUT).
4. *Geographically Distributed Real-Time Simulation (GDRTS) or Geographically Distributed Hardware-in-the-Loop (GDHIL)*: Geographically distributed real time simulations refer to the interconnection of at least two remote laboratories over the internet to realise experiments that harness the capabilities of the interconnected laboratories.
5. *Coupling of Multiple Entities*: As here the coupling of mature software and hardware with simulated and physical infrastructure is possible, a level of TRL6 can be reached (e.g., non-real time simulator with real-time simulator).
6. *Other*: Validation methods which do not fit in the other categories such as optimisation or virtual laboratory, as well as those training activities which do not specify a validation method.

Analysis of Activity Plans

Concerning the analysis of the validation methods implemented during the training activities, it was found that all methods defined at earlier stages were already used as reported in the first release of this deliverable.

This is illustrated in Figure 10 and Figure 11. Moreover, it can be seen that the number of activities with Simulation (Monolithic) increased considerably and is not a relegated validation method anymore. Furthermore, the most referred validation method still lies in the category “Other”, which covers any other methodology not included in the list (e.g., virtual laboratory, optimisation, etc.) as well as those training activities which do not specify a validation method.

¹[Definition of TRL Levels by the European Commission](#)

Figure 10: Analysis of validation methods covered by ERIGrid 2.0 project's training activities delivered and in planning by March 2023.

Figure 11: Analysis of validation methods covered by ERIGrid 2.0 project's training activities delivered and in planning up to date.

2.5 Learning Outcomes based on Target Audience and Training Objectives

The development of ERIGrid 2.0 ILOs is based on an understanding of the target audience and training objectives, i.e., the areas where the project aims to provide educational services.

This section will reflect the intended learning outcomes, which were included in the training activity plans, and can be associated with training objectives summarised in the previous section. In this way, the reflection aims to guide the planning on further objectives to address the planned project outcomes.

2.5.1 Intended Learning Outcomes

ILOs can then be formulated as concrete capabilities a learner will be able to perform upon successful completion of a training activity. The formulation of concrete learning outcomes assists in the alignment and coordination of training activities' scopes and enables the systematic assessment of both learning outcomes and success of training modules developed.

Analysis of Intended Learning Outcomes

The characterisation of ILOs is based on the Bloom Taxonomy. According to Bloom Taxonomy, there are six levels of learning/understanding, which are defined as follows:

1. *Knowledge*: Involves recognising or remembering facts, terms, basic concepts, or answers without necessarily understanding their meaning; typical keywords are "memo-rised".

2. *Comprehension*: involves demonstrating an understanding of facts and ideas by organising, summarising, translating, generalising, giving descriptions, and stating the main ideas; typical keywords are “understand, explain, predict”.
3. *Application*: Involves using acquired knowledge to solve problems in new situations. This involves applying acquired knowledge, facts, techniques and rules. Learners should be able to use prior knowledge to solve problems, identify connections and relationships and how they apply in new situations. Typical keywords are “apply, show, illustrate”.
4. *Analysis*: Involves examining and breaking information into component parts, determining how the parts relate to one another, identifying motives or causes, making inferences, and finding evidence to support generalisations; typical keywords are “distinguish, solve, experiment”.
5. *Synthesis*: Involves building a structure or pattern from diverse elements; it also refers to the act of putting parts together to form a whole or bringing pieces of information together to form a new meaning. Typical keywords are “design, formulate, construct”.
6. *Evaluation*: Involves presenting and defending opinions by making judgements about information, the validity of ideas, or quality of work based on a set of criteria; typical keywords are “evaluate, estimate, assess, appraise”.

Figure 12 and Figure 13 present the categorisation of Bloom Levels in the areas covered by ERIGrid 2.0’s training activities analysis performed in the past deliverable release and this release respectively.

Figure 12: Categorisation of Bloom Levels in the areas covered by the training activities of ERIGrid 2.0 by March 2023.

Figure 13: Categorisation of Bloom Levels in the areas covered by the training activities of ERIGrid 2.0 up to date.

By comparing both figures, it can be easily observed that the areas which had not associated activities in the past released of this deliverable, have now been covered. Likewise, the topics which attract the interest of most training activities remain the same (“Distributed Energy Resources” and “Digitalisation of Energy Systems”), with the addition of the topic “ICT in smart grids”. Moreover, all levels of Bloom taxonomy have been covered, with a clear increase in the information activities (“Knowledge”). Furthermore, the “Comprehension” level remains as the most popular categorisation within the activities organised. In summary, “Knowledge” level was achieved in 21 activities, “Comprehension level” in 47, “Application” level in 23, “Analysis” level in 8, “Synthesis” in 6, and “Evaluation” in 1.

A view of the categorisation of Bloom Levels concerning validation methods and tools implemented in the training activities of ERIGrid 2.0 is found in Figure 14 and Figure 15 considering the analysis performed in the past deliverable release (March 2023) and this release respectively.

Figure 14: Categorisation of Bloom Levels in the validation methods and tools covered by ERIGrid 2.0 project by March 2023.

Figure 15: Categorisation of Bloom Levels in the validation methods and tools covered by ERIGrid 2.0 project up to date.

Comparing both figures, it can be said that the validation method “Simulation (Monolithic)” was not covered in the past release of this deliverable, and has been now covered in several activities. According to the statistics, the “Comprehension” level is now the most popular among the activities, while the validation method “Other” stands out as the most used.

2.6 Conclusion of Educational Strategy

The developed methodology for an educational strategy has been successfully applied in this project. The methodology has been matured and disseminated in a conference paper. The prescribed use of the “Bloom’s *revised* taxonomy” as stipulated in the previous report, has been adopted in the paper as well. For reasons of consistency, however, the above analysis remained with the Bloom’s taxonomy.

In contrast with the first iteration of the educational strategy report, it is now established that all intended topics have been covered by at least one activity.

An analysis of intended cognitive level of competence (using Bloom’s taxonomy) reveals also that training activities with higher levels of competence have been considered in the planning of training activity Intended Learning Outcomes, as compared to the previous report. This level adjustment was requested in the previous report, and could be a result of the adjustment in the planning of training schools.

Overall, the ERIGrid 2.0 training programme can be considered successful in terms of reaching the ambitions set for the training scope, activity types, topics, target audiences and validation methods set out in the beginning of the project. A good balance and adaptation to developing trends in the topic areas was obtained.

Recommendations can be formulated for a future application of the here proposed educational strategy approach in a similar project. First, it can be recommended to formulate topic categories in alignment with the topics formulated in the project activity plan to minimise the confusion over topics classifications. In ERIGrid 2.0, we used “topics”, “functional scenarios” and “validation methods” as three topic classifications. Especially the “topics” and “functional scenarios” contained several overlaps, which also led to a redundant counting in the activity classification. The “validation methods” on the other hand were different, rather orthogonal to the topics. It can be recommended to create a consolidated list of topics based on more generic classifiers, possibly using orthogonal concepts to minimize the overlap in the classification process. This clear classification or glossary leads to a useful disambiguation, with many useful implications, but it is not a trivial challenge, which has also been discussed in (Raussi et al., 2023). Second, it would facilitate the evaluation process to establish clear guidelines for the formulation of ILOs. In the same vein, it would be natural to have the training ambitions for the

project topics formulated in terms of Bloom's Taxonomy competence levels. Finally, it would help to develop a shared and electronic method for activity evaluation and feedback for all training activities in the project early in the project lifecycle, so that the results can more easily be collected and analysed.

The efficacy of the educational strategy approach seems to be confirmed with the results obtained in ERIGrid 2.0, but it is also apparent that the active management and steering of the training outcomes is more resource intensive than an uncoordinated approach.

3 Training Activities

Training activities reported in this section include all those activities organised as part of ERI-Grid 2.0 in the period from March 2023 until January 2025, and which are associated with a specific time and place. Training activities held prior to March 2023 have been reported in Deliverable D4.1 (*D-NA3.1a Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges, 2023*), but are included in the following tables, *italicised*, to offer a complete overview of the activities during the whole project duration.

Digital training activities of ERIGrid 2.0 are reported in Deliverables D4.3 (*D-NA3.2 Education and Training Material for E-learning and Laboratory Education, 2023*) and D4.4 (*D-NA3.3 Lessons Learned and Recommendations for Laboratory Education and E-learning Tools, 2025*). Detailed activity plans of all activities are included in Appendix A.3, which are paired with a more detailed activity report for all activities except for those included in Section 3.4 as Sessions at Conferences.

3.1 Training Schools for Researchers

Training schools for researchers are targeted at PhD students and early stage researchers, aiming to equip them with knowledge and experience required to perform advanced research in the field. The purpose of these schools is to convey state-of-the-art and fundamental techniques, experience with research tools and laboratories, as well as relevant industrial applications. In addition to classic summer and winter schools, also a virtual training programme was offered.

The following Table 1 provides an overview of the organised Training schools. A brief summary of each event is provided in the sections below.

Table 1: Planned and organised Training Schools; the scope column refers to the project's Functional Scenarios.

Title	Hosting Partner	Partners	Scope	Participants		Material
				Total	Internal	
<i>Introduction to Real Time Digital Simulation with Applications in Sustainable Energy Systems (Jan. 2023)^a</i>	TUD	ICCS, UoS	FS1, FS5	12	2	Materials, Report in D-NA3.1a
Digitalisation of Smart Energy Systems (Feb. 2024)	AIT	—	FS6	120	15	Materials, Appendix A.3
Advanced operation and control of active distribution networks: 2nd Edition (Jun. 2024)	ICCS, HEDNO	DERlab, TUD, UCY	FS1, FS2, FS5, FS6	24	16	Appendix A.3
Sector coupling for Electricity and District Energy Systems (March 2025)	DTU	AIT, TUD	FS3, FS6	<i>planned</i>		—

^aActivity reported in (*D-NA3.1a Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges, 2023*)

3.1.1 Implemented Training Schools

Training School on “Advanced Operation and Control of Active Distribution Networks: 2nd Edition”

Five years after the success of the ERIGrid Summer School², ERIGrid 2.0 project partners ICCS-NTUA and HEDNO organized the 2nd Summer School on “Advanced Operation and Control of Active Distribution Networks”, in Athens, Greece, on 3-6 June 2024. The organization of the event was supported by DERlab. Building on the topics covered in the previous Summer School, the follow up school enhanced and extended the topics elaborated in the previous one. The program featured contributions from world class universities, including TUDelft, UCY, KAUST, University of Vaasa, University of Peloponnese. Additionally, PROTASIS S.A., a leading industrial company with an extensive portfolio of successful energy projects, provided a live demonstration and shared industrial experiences on HIL testing of industrial power plant controllers for Renewable Energy System (RES).

Distribution networks have a key role in the transformation of the energy system, characterised by the massive integration of distributed generation, storage and electric vehicles, adoption of ICT solutions and consumer engagement. The aim of the school was to address those topics, highlighting the role of HIL simulation as an efficient tool for developing and testing smart control strategies. The school provided a mixture of lectures and hands-on laboratory sessions, an industry session with the Greek distribution network operator HEDNO, including discussions with industry experts and visits to real installations, and a visit to the Meltemi smart grid pilot site (awarded by the Smart Grids European Technology Platform) at a seaside location a few kilometres away from Athens.

Summary of Activity

A mix of PhD students and young researchers attended the school, with a total of 24 participants. A certificate of attendance was provided to the participants who attended all sessions. More details of the event (agenda, pictures, etc.) are presented in the annex of this report.

- *Day 1:* The first day started with a welcome and introduction to the summer school. The day’s educational sessions centered around the theme “Control & Ancillary Services of DERs”. The lectures started with an insightful session on microgrids and their role as building blocks in smart grid systems. This was followed by a lecture that discussed the hierarchical control of microgrids, focusing on the primary and secondary control layers. The day continued with lectures on advanced laboratory testing of active distribution networks and highlights on advanced ancillary services provided by Photovoltaic (PV) & storage units. The first day of the summer school concluded with a laboratory session and valuable industrial insights from PROTASIS S.A. on HIL Testing of Industrial Power Plant Controllers for RES applications.
- *Day 2:* The second day’s educational sessions focused on the theme “Digitalization of Power Systems”. The first lecture explored the path towards digitalised centralised protection for modern power systems applying 5G. This was followed by a lecture on recent deep learning advances to energy forecasting. The subsequent two lectures discussed cybersecurity considerations of active distribution networks and load frequency control in smart energy systems. The day concluded with an engaging laboratory session. The first part featured a live demonstration by TUD on cybersecurity aspects of digital substations.

²<https://erigrd.eu/successful-erigrd-summer-school-advanced-operation-and-control-of-active-distribution-networks/>

In the second part, the students were divided into 4 groups and attended the hands-on session on CHIL testing of inverter controls.

- *Day 3:* On the third day, the event was hosted by HEDNO with visits arranged to showcase their infrastructure. The day was initiated with a tour of the Attica Distribution Network Control Center, followed by a visit to the HEDNO Laboratories of Electricity Meters and Measurement Transformers. Throughout the day, HEDNO experts facilitated sessions to address questions and engage in discussions with participants.
- *Day 4:* The fourth day's educational sessions developed around the theme "Efficient, flexible & resilient operation of power systems". The first lecture introduced the attendees to decentralized control strategies and the application of blockchain technology. This was followed by a session demonstrating how flexibility can be effectively leveraged in smart distribution networks. The next lecture explored the integration of electric mobility into power systems, while the final lecture provided valuable insights into assessing and enhancing power system resilience. The day concluded with a visit to Meltemi Camp pilot site in Rafina, a seaside area in the suburbs of Athens. This innovative site, recognized by the Smart Grids European Technology Platform, provided attendees with a direct insight into advanced smart grid technologies in practice.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

The school provided PhD students and young researchers with a mixture of lectures, practical laboratory sessions, industry sessions and visits to modern installations. Specifically, the attendees learned about:

- Microgrids, smart grids and hierarchical control
- Advanced laboratory testing methods, with emphasis on Hardware-in-the-Loop
- Digitalisation of power systems
- Cybersecurity of active distribution networks
- Provision of flexibility and demand response
- Integration of electric mobility in power systems
- Machine learning, block chain and forecasting models
- Power system resilience

Training School on "Digitalisation of Smart Energy Systems"

ERIGrid 2.0, in collaboration with the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Framework Program (H2020) SINERGY³ project related to smart and innovate energy management and Smart Energy Systems (SES) European Research Area Network (ERA-Net) RESili8⁴ project related to resilience in Cyber-Physical Energy Systems (CPES), organized a successful online training series on the digitalisation of smart energy systems from February 19-22, 2024.

The online lecture series on the digitalisation of smart energy systems aimed to equip participants with a comprehensive understanding of the latest advancements and methodologies in the field. The primary objectives were to enhance knowledge on the modelling and simulation

³<https://project-sinergy.org>

⁴<https://www.resili8-project.eu>

of integrated energy systems, address cyber security issues, and explore analytical services. Additionally, the series focused on designing and validating CPES and utilizing cyber-physical test beds to validate large-scale smart grid applications. The training sought to prepare students, young professionals, and researchers to effectively contribute to the evolving landscape of smart energy systems by covering these topics.

Summary of Activity

The online training series on the digitalisation of smart energy systems consisted of four comprehensive lectures, each lasting 2 hours with the following content:

- *Lecture “Modelling and Simulation of Integrated Energy Systems”*: The first lecture focused on the modelling and simulation of integrated energy systems, providing insights into advanced techniques and tools for effective energy system integration.
- *Lecture “Integrated Energy Services, Cyber Security Issues, and Analytical Services”*: The second lecture addressed integrated energy services and cyber security issues, highlighting the importance of securing smart energy systems and exploring various analytical services.
- *Lecture “Designing and Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems”*: The third lecture delved into the design and validation of cyber-physical energy systems, emphasizing the methodologies for creating robust and reliable systems.
- *Lecture “Cyber-Physical Tests Beds for Validation of Large-Scale Smart Grid Apps”*: Finally, the fourth lecture covered cyber-physical test beds for the validation of large-scale smart grid applications, showcasing practical approaches to testing and validating smart grid technologies.

This series aimed to equip participants with the necessary skills and knowledge to navigate the evolving landscape of smart energy systems. In total, 120 participants from academia and industry participated in this lecture series. The recordings have been made public and available at the project’s Zenodo Community and the linked YouTube Channel (Widl et al., 2024).

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

The online training series on the digitalisation of smart energy systems achieved several key milestones and provided valuable learning outcomes for participants:

- *Enhanced Knowledge*: Participants gained a deeper understanding of advanced modelling and simulation techniques for integrated energy systems.
- *Cyber Security Awareness*: The training highlighted the importance of cyber security in smart energy systems, equipping attendees with strategies to address potential threats.
- *Practical Skills*: Through the design and validation of CPES, participants developed practical skills essential for creating robust and reliable systems.
- *Hands-On Experience*: The use of cyber-physical test beds for validating large-scale smart grid applications provided hands-on experience, enabling participants to apply theoretical knowledge in practical scenarios.

Impressions from the Event

Impressions from the online training school are provided in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Impressions from the online training lecture series from ERIGrid 2.0, SINERGY, and Resili8 in February 2024.

3.1.2 Planned Training Schools

Training School on “Sector Coupling for Electricity and District Energy Systems”

To accommodate an affordable renewable energy supply the energy system needs to become further integrated with access and flow of flexibility resources across several sectors. This transition requires improved monitoring and more dynamic operation of the thermal energy systems of buildings and district heating networks.

This summer school introduced tools and methods to investigate sector coupling across electricity and district heat networks. Sector coupling solutions and use cases were presented, the relevant control and operational interactions described. The testing and validation of sector coupling use cases and solutions was demonstrated using state of the art simulation tools, laboratory experiments and visits to the field sites.

Hosting location: Risø Campus, Technical University of Denmark, Roskilde, Denmark

Planned hosting period: 10-14th March 2025

3.2 Training Events for Students, Professionals, and the Public

Dedicated events have been organised also for target groups outside the research spectrum, including High School Students (HSSs), Professionals (P), and the General Public (GP) audience. The following Table 2 provides an overview of the organised training events. A brief outline of the event organised in the scope period of this report is provided in the following sections.

Table 2: Organised Training Events for High School Student, Professionals, and the General Public.

Title	Partner	Audience	Venue	Attendees	Date
<i>Environmental education through the construction of a PV module^a</i>	ICCS	HSS	Ekali, Greece	20	30/03, 7, 11/04/2022
<i>Nuffield Research Placements at Strathclyde – Supporting Sustainable Aviation^a</i>	UoS	HSS	UoS DSPL, Glasgow, UK	7	25/07-05/08/2022
<i>European Researcher's Night (ERN) 2020^a</i>	AIT	GP	virtual	>1,000	27/11/2020
<i>European Researcher's Night (ERN) 2022^a</i>	AIT	GP	Vienna, Austria	>1,000	30/09/2022
Goals and challenges of the future electricity markets	HEDNO	P	Athens, Greece	80	13/07/2023

^aActivity reported in (*D-NA3.1a Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges, 2023*)

Training of professionals on “Goals and Challenges of the Future Electricity Markets”

This activity, hosted by HEDNO, took place at the HEDNO offices in the centre of Athens, Greece. More than 80 people attended this training event, all of whom were professionals in the energy sector.

Summary of Activity

Eleven presentations were given during this 7-hour event, presented by professors from academia as well as experts from the industry community. More specifically, the topics presented were the following:

- Introduction to electricity markets: the example of Greece,
- Energy communities, local energy markets and energy management tools,
- Smart grids and remote metering,
- Demand response: from theory to practice,
- Synthetic inertia from power electronics in networks with high renewables penetration,
- Flexibility in the optimal management of electricity distribution networks,
- New challenges in network design and planning,
- Storage systems connected to the network or user facilities,
- Development prospects of electromobility and implications for the energy sector,
- The role of electric vehicles in future power grids, and
- Electromobility market—the present and next steps based on national and European framework.

Since this event also had an industry engagement component, it is also reported in Deliverable D2.8 (*D-NA1.4b Report on Industry Engagement Endeavours, 2025*).

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

The participants of the event familiarized themselves with a wide variety of modern topics in electric power systems, including Electricity markets, Energy communities, Smart grids, Remote metering, Demand response, Power electronics, Power flexibility, Network design and planning, Storage systems, and Electromobility.

3.3 Workshops and Seminars

Workshops and seminars are on-site events organised separately from a conference, and, typically, they are targeting researchers from academia and industry at all levels. The following Table 3 provides an overview of the organised events, whereas a brief outline is provided in the sections below.

2nd Expert Workshop on Design and Operation of Digitalized Sector-Coupled Energy Systems (DigiSect 2023)

The 2-day workshop aimed to bring together experts from Europe to exchange insights and to create a roadmap on possible trends and research directions for operation, control and digitalisation in sector-coupled energy systems and sector integration. It was organised by AIT Austrian Institute of Technology, Hamburg University of Technology, OFFIS–Institute for Information Technology and KTH Royal Institute of Technology, and in cooperation with Wien Energie, the workshop was also supported by ERIGRID 2.0 and the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) Power and Energy Society (PES) Chapter Austria⁵.

Summary of Activity

The workshop contributions were attributed to the following thematic clusters:

- *Cluster 1–System Architecture and Operation Strategies*: focus on applications and best practices for sector coupling and sector integration both on system and component levels, including pilot sites, energy communities, innovative technologies, markets and regulation, etc.
- *Cluster 2–Automation and Digitalization Technologies*: focus on digital technologies enabling sector coupling and sector integration, including artificial intelligence, digital twins, IoT and communication, cyber security, simulation, etc.

The workshop material has been made publicly available at the website of AIT⁶.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

The participants presented their work, exchanged ideas, and discussed the next steps in energy research on how to reach the ambitious policy goals towards energy transition. Sector coupling and digitisation must go hand in hand to support the energy transition as effectively as possible. Innovative digital technologies—e.g., AI, digital twins, and dataspace—will play an important role in this. The integration of these technologies at the system level, considering domain-specific constraints, will be a key factor.

⁵<https://www.ieee-austria.org/index.php/chapters/43-pes>

⁶<https://www.ait.ac.at/themen/power-system-digitalisation/digisect-2023>

Table 3: Overview of organised Workshops and Seminars.

Title	Partner	Venue	Attendees	Material	Date
<i>Supporting a global energy transition: from local energy communities to global simulation networks^a</i>	JRC	JRC, Ispra, Italy	47	Materials	9-10/11/2022
<i>EU ERIGrid 2.0 and NSF IRES US-PRISM Joint Workshop^a</i>	UoS, TUD, ICCS	TUD, Delft, Netherlands	7	see <i>Report^a</i>	15/07/2022
<i>ICT for automation in smart grid and its cybersecurity challenges^a</i>	SINTEF	SINTEF, Trondheim, Norway	31	Materials	30-31/01/2023
<i>Overview of the EU Horizon 2020 ERIGrid 2.0 Project^a</i>	ICCS, UoS	IIT Bhubaneswar, India	30-35	Annex Report	16/02/2023
2 nd Expert Workshop on Design and Operation of Digitalized Sector-Coupled Energy Systems (DigiSect 2023)	AIT, OFFIS	AIT, Vienna, Austria	30	Materials , Appendix A.3	20-21/04/2023
Advanced Laboratory Testing Methods for Modern Power Systems	AIT, DTU, UoS, VTT	TU Dortmund, Dortmund, Germany	35	Course Info , Appendix A.3	08-10/05/2023
3 rd Expert Workshop on Design and Operation of Digitalized Sector-Coupled Energy Systems (DigiSect 2024)	AIT, OFFIS	KTH, Stockholm, Sweden	50	Materials , Appendix A.3	16-17/05/2024
Qualification and Validation of Grid Services from the grid-forming inverters of Hybrid and Renewable Energy Plants	AIT, KEMA, UoS, DERlab, IEE	AIT, Vienna, Austria	25	Workshop Info , Appendix A.3	20/06/2024
Research Infrastructure Automation Workshop 2024	DTU, AIT, RSE, TUD	DTU, Roskilde, Denmark	45	Materials , Appendix A.3	24-25/09/2024
Seminar on Simulation and Testing Methods for Modern Power Systems 2025	OFFIS, AIT, IEE	TU Dortmund	35	Materials , Appendix A.3	21/01/2025

^aActivity reported in (*D-NA3.1a Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges, 2023*)

For this challenge, the DigiSect 2023 workshop offered a forum for in-depth discussions on tools for validation and implementation of projects. Furthermore, a dedicated interactive session focusing on the alignment of future developments for system-level validation tools and methods with the foreseeable European research agenda was held.

Since this workshop also had an industry engagement component, it is also reported in Deliverable D2.8 (*D-NA1.4b Report on Industry Engagement Endeavours, 2025*).

Advanced Laboratory Testing Methods for Modern Power Systems

The Electric Energy Systems University Enterprise Training Partnership (EES-UETP) is a collaborative initiative to enhance professionals' skills and knowledge in electric energy systems through specialized courses and training events organised by European Universities. Several ERIGrid 2.0 partners like DTU, NTUA, UCY, and UoS are part of this training partnership.

Summary of Activity

In May 2023, TU Dortmund organised a three-day training event related to advanced testing methods for power systems as part of the EES-UETP collaboration. This event was notably linked with the International Energy Agency (IEA)'s Technology Cooperation Program (TCP) International Smart Grid Action Network (ISGAN)⁷, specifically through the Smart Grid International Research Facility Network (SIRFN)⁸ and its ERIGrid 2.0 cooperation. This connection facilitated a collaborative environment for testing and evaluating smart grid technologies. The event also featured significant contributions from ERIGrid 2.0, which supports smart grid and smart energy systems research. Lectures covering ERIGrid 2.0 results were provided by experts from several leading institutions, including AIT, DTU, UoS, and VTT.

These contributions enriched the event with cutting-edge insights and practical knowledge, fostering a deeper understanding of the latest advancements in electric energy systems, especially related to validation and testing methods. Participants had the opportunity to engage in hands-on sessions, discussions, and networking activities, which further enhanced their learning experience and facilitated the exchange of ideas and best practices in the field.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

This event achieved significant milestones in the field of advanced laboratory testing for modern power systems. The workshop provided an extensive view of laboratory testing methods (incl. HIL-based approaches). Participants (mainly students and researchers) gained insights into validation techniques using CHIL and PHIL approaches, co-simulation with geographically distributed laboratories, and testing of multi-domain energy systems.

Key learning outcomes included understanding the integration of ICT into power systems, enhancing cybersecurity and protection measures, and exploring relevant use cases. The event facilitated the exchange of ideas between industry specialists and researchers, discussing state-of-the-art technologies, solutions, and future trends. Real-life experiences and examples, ranging from early-stage research to daily operations, were shared, providing participants with practical knowledge and hands-on experiences through laboratory tutorials at the Smart Grid Technology Lab and the Protection and Automation Lab of the TU Dortmund University. This comprehensive approach ensured that attendees were left with a deeper understanding of the theoretical and practical challenges in modern power systems and the innovative solutions being developed to address them.

Impressions from the Event

Impressions from the training course are provided in Figure 17.

⁷<https://www.iea-isgan.org>

⁸https://www.iea-isgan.org/our-work3/wg_5/

Figure 17: Impressions from the EES-UETP training course in May 2023 at TU Dortmund.

3rd Expert Workshop on Design and Operation of Digitalized Sector-Coupled Energy Systems (DigiSect 2024)

The third edition of this workshop, held on May 16-17 in Stockholm, Sweden, 2024, aimed to gather experts from across Europe to share insights and develop a roadmap for future trends and research directions in the operation, control, and digitalization of sector-coupled energy systems. Organised by KTH Royal Institute of Technology, AIT Austrian Institute of Technology, Hamburg University of Technology, and OFFIS–Institute for Information Technology, the workshop was also supported by Digital Futures, Dig-IT Lab, KTH Energy Platform & KTH Digitalization Platform, IEEE PES & Power Electronics Society (PELS) Joint Chapter Sweden⁹, IEEE PES Chapter Austria, and ERIGrid 2.0.

Summary of Activity

The workshop contributions were categorised quite similar to last year's editions into the following two thematic clusters:

- *Cluster 1–System Architecture and Operation Strategies:* Focused on applications and best practices for sector coupling and integration at both system and component levels. Topics included pilot sites, energy communities, innovative technologies, markets, and regulation.
- *Cluster 2–Automation and Digitalization Technologies:* Emphasized digital technologies that enable sector coupling and integration, such as artificial intelligence, digital twins, IoT and communication, cybersecurity, and simulation.

The workshop material has been made publicly available at the website of Digital Futures from KTH Royal Institute of Technology¹⁰.

⁹<https://r8.ieee.org/sweden/pepel-chapter>

¹⁰<https://www.digitalfutures.kth.se/event/3rd-expert-workshop-on-design-and-operation-of-digitalized-sector-coupled-energy-systems-digisect-2024-on-16-17-may/>

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

Participants presented their work, exchanged ideas, and discussed the next steps in energy research to achieve ambitious policy goals for energy transition. The workshop highlighted the necessity of integrating sector coupling and digitization to support the energy transition effectively. Innovative digital technologies, including Artificial Intelligence (AI), digital twins, and dataspace, were identified as crucial components. The integration of these technologies at the system level, considering domain-specific constraints, was deemed essential.

The DigiSect 2024 workshop provided a platform for in-depth discussions on tools for validation and project implementation. Additionally, an interactive session focused on aligning future developments for system-level validation tools and methods with the anticipated European research agenda.

Since this workshop also had an industry engagement component, it is also reported in Deliverable D2.8 (*D-NA1.4b Report on Industry Engagement Endeavours, 2025*).

Qualification and Validation of Grid Services from the grid-forming inverters of Hybrid and Renewable Energy Plants

ERIGrid 2.0 organised a technical workshop related to the validation of grid services from grid-forming inverters at AIT that also addressed educational topics. This event was held alongside the CIRED 2024 Vienna Workshop¹¹ and focused on the role of grid-forming inverters in providing grid services from hybrid and renewable energy plants, addressing their current and future requirements.

Summary of Activity

A good mix of speakers from industry, research centres, and universities highlighted trends and real-life challenges, emphasising the need for reliable deployment of these services. The workshop covered the qualification and validation of these services and equipment at a system level, with ERIGrid 2.0 experts presenting their findings and ongoing research. Participants had the opportunity to witness advanced testing in a research laboratory and network with colleagues. The event included also a lab tour through the AIT SmartEST Research Infrastructure (RI) where a live demo on inertia control was provided. Supported by the IEEE PES Austria Chapter and IEA ISGAN/SIRFN, the workshop attracted around 25 participants from academia and industry.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

The workshop demonstrated approaches and experiences in the qualification and validation of grid services from grid-forming inverters of hybrid and renewable energy plants. Participants gained insights into current trends, real-life challenges, and the importance of reliable deployment of these services. They also learned about the testing and validation processes at a system level, enhancing their understanding of advanced testing methods and their practical applications.

Since this workshop also had an industry engagement component, it is also reported in Deliverable D2.8 (*D-NA1.4b Report on Industry Engagement Endeavours, 2025*).

¹¹<https://www.cired2024vienna.org/>

Impressions from the Event

Impressions from the training-related event are provided in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Impressions from the CIREN 2024 Vienna Workshop side event in June 2024 at AIT.

Research Infrastructure Automation Workshop

The workshop topic centred on various issues relevant for advancing smart energy research infrastructures, with a focus on acceleration and digitalisation opportunities.

Summary of Activity

The workshop content was defined by the three main session themes:

- *Collaboration*: metadata and digital tools for facilitating research collaboration and data exchange
- *Automation*: how energy system test setups can be repeatable and reproducible (and less complex to handle)
- *Coupling of Test Facilities*: Methods, Techniques and Technologies to couple large scale test resources from multiple RIs

The event was organized in these main sessions, with additional lab tours and a dinner in the SYSLAB facilities. The main sessions included 4-5 presentations and a panel discussion with the speakers, each. This frame gave ample opportunity for participants to engage and interact with another. Especially the lab-tours and dinner offered a fruitful setting to connect.

The workshop was co-organized with the RISEnergy and NEST projects and the IEA-ISGAN-SIRFN network, but the organization was firmly anchored in ERIGrid 2.0. Speakers were invited and facilitated by the co-organising partners: RISEnergy participants (from FZ Juelich, BRGM) with some overlapping participation from RISEnergy/ERIGrid 2.0, e.g., from AIT, NTUA and DTU). A number of presentations were included and facilitated by the ISGAN-SIRFN network. The workshop included an open discussion on how the community assembled at the workshop may carry on, e.g. through projects like RISEnergy, and a 2025 instance of the workshop was anticipated by several participants.

All presentations slides and workshop notes have been made publicly available via Zenodo, see (Heussen & Gehrke, 2024).

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

The workshop achieved to create a new topic-setting event, with a potential of creating and maintaining a research community beyond the ERIGrid 2.0 project scope. In that respect, the most motivating outcome of the event was that a participant volunteered host of “the RI Automation Workshop 2025”. Several participants approached the organisers, congratulating for a well-organized and successful workshop. Apart from the inspired presentations and the productive panel discussions, a concrete outcome from the workshop were the discussions hosted in the wrap-up session.

An insight gathered from the workshop and discussions was how important the international network is for RI automation topics, since there is an opportunity to leverage the network for common challenges, once the initial diversity of viewpoints is overcome. First, current relevant international networks and projects were identified, beyond ERIGrid 2.0, including DERLab, IEA ISGAN SIRFN, IEA PVPS (Task 19 on PV grid integration), IEA DHC Annex TS9 (district heating and cooling, lab facilities), and several IEEE Working Groups and Task Forces (cf. slides).

Several common Smart Energy RI related challenges were identified, where independent parallel developments could be avoided and pooled into common initiatives, enabling also further alignment in the community:

- Scaling-up tools (generally: any automation, if interoperable, is also important for scaling up and accelerating the time-to-experiment)
- Multi-RI configuration management
- Test data documentation and research exchange (meta-data, ontologies, research data-spaces)
- Open Test Case repository for ease of entry to the field and for starting complex test collaborations
- Need for offering a landscape of tools – mapping vs. requirements
- Challenges around the topic of *Reproducibility of experiments*
 - Documentation , parameters, packages
 - Result comparison
 - Confidence in results
 - Deterministic frames of analysis vs. Statistical influences
 - Lab vs. simulation

Participants agreed that several of the concepts and open software ideas presented at the workshop were worth to follow up on at a community level. For example, the scaling and reproducibility enhancing tools “uAPI”, “Configuration Management” and “Kubernetes-netem” as well as the “OpenSVP” platform were shortlisted as specific tools with sufficient community backing to follow beyond the project ERIGrid 2.0 scope.

The discussion notes have been included in the “Wrap-up Session Notes¹²” as part of the related Zenodo release.

Since this workshop also had an industry engagement component, it is also reported in Deliverable D2.8 (*D-NA1.4b Report on Industry Engagement Endeavours, 2025*).

Seminar on Simulation and Testing Methods for Modern Power Systems

The course on simulation and testing methods for modern power systems was organised by TU Dortmund. It aimed to provide knowledge on advanced simulation and testing methods covering both theoretical aspects and practical applications such as HIL, CHIL, PHIL, testing and validation methods, electrical design of low-voltage laboratory, and practical testing examples in modern energy systems.

Summary of Activity

This seminar was held at TU Dortmund on 21 January 2025 as part of the course. There were five presentations from different research institutes:

- Sector-coupling emulation for PHIL, Technical University of Munich
- PHIL: the experiment facility at Energy Lab 2.0, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
- Why testing matters? smart grid testing chain with a practical example, OFFIS Institute for Information Technology
- HIL testing infrastructure and praxis-relevant applications, Fraunhofer IEE
- HIL-based evaluation of power and energy system applications, AIT Austrian Institute of Technology

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

The seminar provided valuable insights and experiences on HIL testing, with practical examples including sector coupling between electrical and heating grids, hydrogen technology, and system integrity protection systems. Additionally, the holistic testing approach developed in ERIGrid 2.0 was presented, laying the groundwork for validation and testing concepts.

Test cases from the ERIGrid 2.0 project were also shared with students, serving as a knowledge hub to support the development of new test cases based on these examples. The seminar fostered interactive discussions and exchanges between speakers and students about methods and RI for real-time simulation.

A key takeaway from the seminar was the importance of collaboration among research institutes to facilitate access and knowledge. The ERIGrid 2.0 project exemplifies this by providing transnational access opportunities for students, practitioners, and industry, enabling them to benefit from advanced RIs in Europe.

3.4 Sessions at Conferences

An overview of organised sessions and activities at scientific conferences and events is provided in Table 4, whereas a brief summary of them is provided in the following sections.

¹²https://zenodo.org/records/14699238/files/Wrap-up_Session_Notes.pdf?download=1

Table 4: Overview of organised tutorials, special and panel sessions.

Title	Type ^a	Partner	Conference	Attendees	Date
<i>Real-time simulation advancing education and training on power and energy systems^b</i> Session website	PS	ICCS	IEEE PES General Meeting 2021	n/a	27/07/2021
<i>Coordinated Control and Co-Simulation of Power Systems in Energy Internet^b</i> Session website	PS	UoS	IEEE PES General Meeting 2022	30	18/07/2022
<i>Validating Smart Energy Systems^b</i> Tutorial materials	T	AIT	IEEE SMC 2022	5	09/10/2022
<i>Pushing the Boundaries of Real-Time Simulations for Validation of Future Complex Power Systems^b</i> Session website	PS	UoS, AIT, ICCS	IEEE ISGT Europe 2022	28	11/10/2022
Emerging skill needs and training tools for professionals and researchers in the field of smart energy systems Tutorial Material	T	ICCS, AIT	IEEE OSMSES 2023	30-35	28/03/2023
Open-source models for research and training in smart energy systems	PS	ICCS, AIT, JRC	IEEE OSMSES 2023	30-35	28/03/2023
Designing and Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems	T	AIT	IEEE SMC 2023	10	01/10/2023
Development, Management and Applications of Open-Source Smart Energy Systems Education	PS	ICCS, UCY	IEEE OSMSES 2024	Approx. 30	09/04/2024
Approaches, Methods, and Tools for the Engineering and Validation of Cyber-Physical Energy Systems	T	AIT	IEEE SMC 2024	6	06/10/2024

^aTutorial (T), Special Session (SS), and Panel Session (PS)

^bActivity reported in (*D-NA3.1a Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges, 2023*)

3.4.1 Tutorials

Tutorial “Emerging Skill Needs and Training Tools for Professionals and Researchers in the Field of Smart Energy Systems”

The tutorial “Emerging Skill Needs and Training Tools for Professionals and Researchers in the Field of Smart Energy Systems” was organized by ICCS and supported by AIT.

Summary of Activity

The tutorial presented in the IEEE conference, 2023 Open Source Modelling and Simulation of Energy Systems, held in March 2023. It was motivated by the urgent need to upskill professionals and researchers in response to the ongoing energy transition, which demands new competencies in digitalisation and smart energy systems. Identified skill gaps were presented and innovative teaching methods (IEEE PES Task Force experiences) for modern power systems were discussed. To bridge these gaps, advanced, open-access educational tools developed in the frame of ERIGrid 2.0, and advanced laboratory methodologies, like HIL, were showcased. Modern tools and validation methods provide practical resources to enhance workforce readiness and innovation in the evolving energy industry.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

The event successfully highlighted key achievements, including identifying critical skill gaps in the energy sector as revealed by the ERIGrid 2.0 and EDDIE projects, showcasing innovative teaching methodologies identified in IEEE PES Task Force, and demonstrating modern simulation and HIL techniques for smart energy systems. Additionally, participants were introduced to advanced educational tools developed within the ERIGrid 2.0 project to support ongoing professional and research development. As a result, attendees gained insights into evolving competency needs in power systems driven by digitalisation, were introduced to innovative teaching methods and available open source educational tools, and acquired practical knowledge of advanced simulation and validation approaches, equipping them with valuable resources for future learning and upskilling in modern energy systems.

Tutorial “Designing and Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems” at IEEE SMC 2023

The tutorial “Validating Smart Energy Systems” at IEEE SMC 2023, organised by AIT and hosted by the IEEE Systems, Man, and Cybernetics Society, focused on the integration and validation of renewable energy resources within smart grids.

Summary of Activity

The event covered essential topics such as the ERIGrid 2.0 vision, validation and testing approaches, and methods and tools for system-level validation. Participants were introduced to various validation examples and educational tools, providing a comprehensive overview of the current state and future needs in designing and validating CPES.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

The tutorial highlighted the increasing complexity of future energy systems, especially with higher penetration levels of renewable energy. It emphasised the importance of system-level design and validation approaches, combining simulations and laboratory testing, including HIL methods. Attendees gained valuable insights into the necessary validation methods and tools, preparing them to address the challenges in the evolving energy landscape. The event successfully equipped researchers, academics, and engineers with the knowledge and skills needed for effective system-level validation and testing in smart energy systems.

Tutorial “Approaches, Methods, and Tools for the Engineering and Validation of Cyber-Physical Energy Systems” at IEEE SMC 2024

The tutorial “Approaches, Methods, and Tools for the Engineering and Validation of Cyber-Physical Energy Systems” at IEEE SMC 2024, organised by AIT and hosted by the IEEE Systems, Man, and Cybernetics Society, focused on addressing the complexities and engineering challenges of CPES.

Summary of Activity

The event covered critical topics such as engineering problems, design and validation approaches, and methods for test preparation. Participants were introduced to integrated design and validation techniques, as well as collaborative tools for team-based engineering efforts, providing a comprehensive overview of the current state and future needs in this domain.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

The tutorial emphasized the increasing complexity of future energy systems, particularly with varying levels of renewable energy integration. It highlighted the necessity of system-level design and validation approaches to manage these complexities effectively. Attendees gained valuable insights into engineering and validation methods, preparing them to tackle the challenges in the evolving energy landscape. The event successfully equipped researchers, academics, and engineers with the knowledge and skills needed for effective system-level design and validation in CPES.

3.4.2 Special and Panel Sessions

Special Panel “Open-source Models for Research and Training in Smart Energy Systems”

The panel session “Open-source Models for Research and Training in Smart Energy Systems” was organized by ICCS and supported by AIT and JRC. The panel session took place at IEEE conference, 2023 Open Source Modelling and Simulation of Energy Systems, held in March 2023.

Summary of Activity

This panel session presented advances in open-source models, methodologies, and resources for research and education in smart energy systems, highlighting the importance of freely available tools and comprehensive documentation for enhancing practical skills, fostering collaboration, and driving innovation in power systems analysis. The session began with an introduction by Alexandros Paspatis, followed by presentations on the PreCISE approach for open-source documentation of simulation test cases by Edmind Widl (online), holistic open-source documentation of benchmark energy networks by Evangelos Kotsakis, a benchmark network for hardware-in-the-loop simulation by Panos Kotsampopoulos (online), and the role of open-source modelling in advancing education in energy systems by Alkistis Kontou. Collectively, these discussions emphasized the value of accessible and standardized resources in empowering a diverse community of researchers, educators, and industry professionals to advance the development of next-generation smart energy systems.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

The panel session highlighted key advancements in open-source models and methodologies for smart energy systems, emphasizing their impact on research, education, and innovation. Open-source initiatives like the PreCISE approach for simulation test cases and holistic documentation of benchmark networks were showcased, demonstrating their significance for both academia and industry. The session also highlighted the role of open-source modeling in enhancing hands-on training for young engineers, fostering practical skills development. Additionally, it promoted the need for standardized, accessible tools to encourage collaboration and equitable resource sharing while integrating advanced techniques, such as hardware-in-the-loop simulation, to support the energy transition.

Panel Session “Development, Management and Applications of Open-Source Smart Energy Systems Education”

The panel session “Development, Management and Applications of Open-Source Smart Energy Systems Education” organized by ICCS and supported by UCY. The panel session took place at the joint event, 2024 Open Source Modelling and Simulation of Energy Systems (OSM-SES 2024) & Symposium Communications for Energy Systems (ComForEn) 2024, held in September 2024.

Summary of Activity

This panel session explored innovative educational approaches for smart energy systems using open-source tools and resources. Rad Stanev (TUS) presented the application of simulation and PHIL techniques in both “laboratory” and “real-life laboratory” environments to enhance smart energy education. George Makrides (UCY) discussed modern open-source learning management systems for real-time supervision and control of smart energy systems. Veit Hagenmeyer (KIT) shared experiences with open-source tools, including PROOF, pyWatts, and eASIMOV, used at KIT. Lastly, Alkistis Kontou (ICCS-NTUA) introduced a methodology for developing and managing open-source educational materials within research projects, as an effective way to disseminate and transfer the output knowledge to students and professionals.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

The panel session achieved valuable insights into advancing smart energy systems education through open-source tools. Presentations demonstrated practical applications of simulation and PHIL environments for hands-on learning, highlighted the use of open-source platforms for real-time system supervision and control, and shared experiences with advanced tools like PROOF, pyWatts, and eASIMOV for data analysis and modeling. Moreover, the methodology developed in the frame of ERIGrid 2.0 for developing and managing open-source educational content within research projects was presented along with lessons learned from its application. Overall, the session promoted the development and use of open-source resources to foster continuous learning and enhance interdisciplinary expertise in smart energy systems.

4 Overview of Staff Exchange and Achievements

4.1 Principles and Method of Staff Exchange

The basis for the staff exchange has already been outlined in the Grant Agreement (GA), i.e., the Description of Action (DoA) (*ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement*, 2019) and detailed in Deliverable D4.1 (*D-NA3.1a Report on the Training Workshops and Staff Exchanges*, 2023). The program aims to foster collaboration and knowledge sharing among project partners. The exchange supports Networking Activities (NAs) and Joint Research Activities (JRAs) by enabling joint work and collaboration on common topics.

With a budget of 20k EUR managed by the coordinator, the exchange process involves continuous submission and evaluation of mini proposals, providing up to 2k EUR for travel and accommodation per exchange. The procedure includes obtaining permission from the host organization, submitting an application, organizing the exchange, executing it, and reporting the outcomes. The content must align with project objectives, and minimal reporting is required. Necessary documents include the Application Form, Summary Report Template, Cost Reimbursement Sheet Template, and Payment Receipt Template.

4.2 Staff Exchange Activities

The following sections provide an overview of the realised staff exchanges during the project's last 22 months, including a summary of these exchanges.

4.2.1 Overview of Realised Staff Exchanges

In the last 22 months, 5 staff exchange applications have been received and all of them were accepted for realisation. Table 5 provides an overview of them.

Table 5: Overview of the realised staff exchanges.

No	Name	Host	Sender	Period	Nature ^a	Researcher
13	JRA3.3 – Configuration Management	TUD	DTU	31/07-03/08/2023	G	O. Gehrke
14	JRA3.3 – Configuration Management	TUD	RWTH	31/07-03/08/2023	G	A. Acosta
15	JRA3.3 – Configuration Management	TUD	OFFIS	31/07-03/08/2023	G	M. Arhum
16	High-fidelity PHIL testing	ICCS	VTT	01/07-09/07/2024	G	K. Sirviö
17	High-fidelity PHIL testing	ICCS	VTT	01/07-09/07/2024	G	V. Ollikainen

^aIndividual Staff Exchange (I), Group Staff Exchange (G)

4.2.2 Summary of Realised Staff Exchanges

Staff Exchange “JRA3.3 – Configuration Management”

Summary of the Activity

The JRA3.3 staff exchange, held from July 31 to August 3, 2023, focused on developing a configuration management approach for multi-RI experiments. Researchers from DTU, RWTH, and OFFIS collaborated at TUD to create and test a proof-of-concept for automating the configuration of data flows and signal mappings. This effort aimed to enhance reproducibility and efficiency in experimental setups.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

The staff exchange successfully developed Python scripts to automate the creation of local configuration files from a global configuration. The configuration management approach was tested with a proof-of-concept, demonstrating its effectiveness. Key lessons learned included the efficiency of software testing and coding in smaller groups and the time-saving benefits of in-person interactions. The results have been further developed and integrated into JRA4 demonstrations, with the code to be made publicly available on the project’s GitHub¹³ page.

The related summary report of this group staff exchange is provided in Appendix B.1.

Staff Exchange “High-fidelity PHIL testing”

Summary of the Activity

The staff exchange on high-fidelity PHIL testing took place from July 1 to July 9, 2024, involving researchers from VTT and hosted by ICCS. The primary goal was to share expertise in constructing PHIL test setups, focusing on stability and accuracy improvements through advanced interface algorithms. This exchange aimed to enhance the visiting researchers’ skills and gather feedback on the developed methodologies.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

The exchange resulted in the development of a comprehensive guide for designing PHIL environments, emphasizing stability and protection schemes. Key achievements included the creation of a Simulink model for stability analysis and the integration of comprehensive protection schemes in RSCAD. Important lessons learned highlighted the critical role of proper filtering techniques, the careful selection of amplifier types, and the necessity of considering time delays for accurate simulations. The project underscored the importance of detailed design and testing in developing advanced power systems, contributing to the resilience and efficiency of future energy infrastructures.

The related summary report of this group staff exchange is provided in Appendix B.2.

¹³<https://github.com/ERIGrid2>

5 Conclusions

This document offered an updated report on training and coordination activities that together helped advance the state of shared knowledge of a broad range of target audiences in the research fields of ERIGrid 2.0.

A methodology for managing the ERIGrid 2.0 training program was developed and presented here in its updated form. The approach enables a quantitative summative assessment of the types of activities, the content and scope, as well as the level of competences achieved by the training. This method was developed and applied during the project to enable a bottom-up creative development of activities and content, while still enabling a steering and coordination of the topics, content, competence levels and target groups. By comparing data from the updated assessment of training activities with data from the previous report and an initial survey on the project ambition, it can be observed that the gap noted in the previous report has been closed. The project achieved overall a balanced set of results, suggesting that the proposed steering methodology was effective.

Several recommendations for a future implementation of an educational program in research projects were formulated. In particular, it would be helpful to define a method of feedback collection from participants in training activities at an early stage, possibly in collaboration with the first activities.

The *on-site training activities* reported covered a wide range of training types, including training for high school students, the general public, and industrial professionals and researchers. The training activities offered a good range and number: Four training schools for PhD students and researchers were planned, of which two physical schools have been implemented and one was implemented as multi-day online training event; the fourth event was planned to be hosted in March 2025. Two events were hosted for high school students and the general public, respectively, and one event was hosted for the training of professionals. Ten workshops were organized and hosted by the project partners, each attracting between seven and 50 participants, attracting a total of 340 researchers and professionals. At international conferences, five panel sessions were organised and four tutorials given. In summary, it can be stated that the performed and planned training activities are fulfilling and exceeding the intended project objectives.

The organisation and content of the ERIGrid 2.0 staff exchange was described. In total 17 staff exchanges were executed. As reported, these knowledge exchange activities significantly enhanced the common understanding of key technologies developed in the project.

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Appendix A: Educational Strategy, Activity Plans and Reports

A.1 Educational Strategy Conference Paper

Educational Programme Management Methodology for Research Projects

Alkistis Kontou^{1*}, Kai Heussen², Leonard Ramos Perez³, Panagiotis A. Karafotis⁴, Mazheruddin Syed⁵, Alexandros Paspatis⁶, and Evangelos Rikos⁷

¹School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, Athens, Greece

²Department of Wind and Energy Systems, Technical University of Denmark, Roskilde, Denmark

³European Distributed Energy Resources Laboratories (DERlab) e.V., Kassel, Germany

⁴Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator (HEDNO), Athens, Greece

⁵Energy Advisory, WSP UK, Glasgow, United Kingdom

⁶Department of Engineering, Manchester Metropolitan University, Manchester, United Kingdom

⁷Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving, Athens, Greece

*alkistiskont@mail.ntua.gr

Abstract—Smart grids and intelligent energy systems play a pivotal role in fostering the sustainable advancement of our civilization. Over the past few decades, power systems, like many other sectors, have undergone a rapid digital transformation. This rapid development necessitates a proactive response from universities, research institutes, industry stakeholders in relation to educational programmes. Educators must rapidly adapt their curricula and teaching methodologies to effectively train the next generation of engineering professionals. While curriculum crafting for new educational programs is inherently challenging, another layer of complexity arises when research collaborations in large consortia are tasked with delivering high-quality education within a given project scope and time frame. This paper outlines a methodology for establishing an educational strategy for such research projects. This approach takes into account the available resources and expertise of the project participants, while embracing modern, learner-centric educational methodologies. It also ensures alignment with broader objectives or frameworks. Furthermore, the strategy incorporates a dynamic evaluation process that runs concurrently with the educational activities. Finally, the ERIGrid 2.0 H2020 project upon which the proposed methodology was developed, is presented as a case study.

Index Terms—educational programme management, educational strategy, training activities.

I. INTRODUCTION

Like in many other industries, the energy landscape has been evolving faster than ever in the past decade with the emergence of new technologies and sciences shaping the future. This accelerated transition poses two challenges in relation to the workforce: (i) the rapid growth of the sector has outpaced the availability of skilled professionals, and (ii) with the emergence of new technologies and sciences, there is a lack of workforce with specialist skills that can ensure the growth and sustainability at pace [1], [2]. Apart from the technical aspects that need to be tackled in the frame of the energy transition, a very important aspect that requires attention is the adaptation and modernization of the power systems education. This gap in availability of skilled professionals highlights the importance of ongoing skills development and training.

To effectively address the gaps in skills shortage, training and skills development at all stages and ages is essential. To educate and prepare the new generation of researchers, engineers and professionals, the curricula across different education levels - primary and secondary school, undergraduate, masters and Ph.D. syllabi - should be updated and enhanced. Furthermore, opportunities for individuals looking to make a change in career through acquiring knowledge should be provided. One instance of this approach is the National Transition Training Fund in Scotland [3]. This initiative financed the creation of a set of short, targeted training programs, known as micro-credentials. These programs were designed for individuals who faced redundancy due to the uncertainties posed by COVID-19. The aim was to help them not only preserve their current employment but also acquire the necessary skills to transition into sectors anticipated to have significant future growth potential [3]. Energy infrastructure related education at the community level is also crucial, as it empowers individuals and local organizations to actively participate in the energy transition, make informed choices, and contribute to a more sustainable and reliable energy future. An example of such an approach funded by H2020 is the MOST (Meaningful Open Schooling Connects Schools To Communities) project that brings together school and community members to focus on scientific approaches to regional sustainable issues ranging from waste management to energy saving [4].

To enhance educational experience, foster the acquisition of fresh skills and abilities, and cultivate a versatile interdisciplinary foundation, it is imperative to utilise the variety of mediums of delivery available. The usual practices of delivery of educational activities such as lectures, seminars, workshops should be complemented by development of e-learning tools and materials, e.g., webinars, online simulation tools, e-books and videos. Learning through hands-on laboratory practices can help assimilate knowledge by bridging the gap between theory and its applications [5]. An example of an action funded by the EU is the EMMA (European Multiple MOOC Aggrega-

tor) platform that aims to demonstrate excellence in pioneering teaching techniques and educational approaches by conducting extensive pilot programs of free delivery of MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses), in multiple languages and broad range of subjects [6].

There is focused effort in development of training and skills through dedicated educational projects. Multiple frameworks have funded several projects focused on engineering education through the years, e.g., projects funded by the Erasmus Europe or Horizon Europe actions in the EU [7], UKRI in the UK [8], and NSF in the USA [9], with elaborate educational methodologies and extensive outcomes, e.g. MOOCs [10], lecture notes [11], student and staff exchanges [12] etc. The challenge identified in this paper focuses on research projects instead. Research projects outnumber projects that have a dedicated focus on education around the world, with their technical aspects covering a wide range of activities, usually extending the existing knowledge/practice. Due to the pace of the energy transition, converting such research outputs to training programmes is of utmost interest, and their effective integration into education is essential. A coordinated effort in bringing research and education together can foster a culture of continuous and innovative learning, paving path towards preparing a highly skilled and agile workforce capable of driving sustainability and growth in the energy sector.

Developing educational curricula, courses and training events is a common practice within the educational community, where frameworks, programme management and pedagogical approaches are well established and utilised. This paper discusses the challenges of development of educational material within research projects, particularly looking at the adoption of typical educational programme management. Having highlighted the challenges, the paper proposes a revised programme management methodology more applicable for adoption by research projects. The application of the methodology to ERIGrid 2.0 (European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition) H2020 project [13], for development and dissemination of research knowledge is reported as case study.

II. EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMME MANAGEMENT FOR SMART ENERGY SYSTEMS

A well aligned educational programme facilitates the coordination of learning and skill development activities in a specific area. This section presents key elements of educational programme management and identifies the opportunities of adopting this methodology for the implementation of an educational strategy in research projects.

A. Elements of Educational Programme Management

The process of development of educational programme management can be divided into three logical stages as: (i) preparation and planning, (ii) implementation and evaluation and (iii) sustainability and compliance, each of them briefly described below.

1) Preparation and Planning: Identification of the target audience is the first step in development of an educational programme management followed by the identification of their needs. It should be acknowledged that students enter formal education with varying levels of prior knowledge, skills, beliefs and concepts that immensely shape their approach to observation of the environment and influences how they structure and comprehend information [14]. A number of methods are typically employed to assess the knowledge and skills the educational programme should address, for example, undertaking research, conducting interviews and surveys. The second step in the development of the educational programme is to ascertain the intended learning objectives and outcomes. More often Bloom's taxonomy is adopted for the purpose of defining the intended learning objectives and outcomes [15]. Once defined, the strategies and methods for delivering the instructions are set. The next step is to define the assessment criteria and approach. Finally, a detailed plan is developed for delivery. It is imperative that situational constraints are taken into consideration when the learning objectives, the instruction strategies and assessments are designed. Additionally, the success of the programme hinges upon timely identification of adequate resources (funding an personnel) for the delivery of the programme.

2) Implementation and Evaluation: The second stage of the programme management involves the execution of the programme as per the designed plan. This involves the delivery of all planned educational activities such as lectures and tutorials. At this stage of the programme, it is essential to continuously monitor its progress. It is important to have quality control measures in place to ensure the high standards. Gathering feedback serves as an opportunity to assess if the programme meets its objectives and to adapt and improve as necessary.

3) Compliance, Promotion and Sustainability: It is important to ensure the developed programme abides by relevant laws and regulations, including educational standards and ethical guidelines. Plan to attain any accreditation are set and reviewed regularly. Throughout the process it is beneficial to engage with necessary stakeholders including learners, teachers, parents and community members to incorporate their input and ensure their support. Development of strategies to promote the programme to attract audience is crucial for the success of the programme. Evaluating the programmes impact and effectiveness is necessary to ensure long-term sustainability of the educational programme. Effective mechanisms for resolving any disputes promptly should be in place. It should be a practice to regularly review and revise the program to adapt to changing needs and circumstances.

B. Challenges in Application of Educational Programme Management to Research Projects

In this section, the challenges in application of educational programme management to research projects are identified. As the methodology of educational programme management outlined above was designed for educational institutions, there

are differences in the requirements of managing educational programmes within a research project. However, we can identify a good number of similarities, which suggest adoption of educational programme management methods summarised above. The following sections first highlight the similarities that warrant adoption, then we identify differences which motivate adaptations to the methodology for application in research projects.

1) *Similarities*: In both, educational programme management and the application to research projects, identifying the target audience is a fundamental step in the development process. The need to accommodate diverse levels of prior knowledge, skills, beliefs, and concepts among the audience is also common in both contexts. Tailoring educational activities to address these varying needs and competences is a shared objective. In both contexts, a course or training activity can be organised around clearly identifiable target competences. The method of defining "intended learning outcomes" as a tangible and testable formulation of the competences, is practice-proven in higher education, and equally applicable to research-based training activities.

Further, the use of Bloom's taxonomy is a widely accepted technique to organise and structure intended learning outcomes, equally relevant for research related competences. In terms of programme implementation, there is in both educational programmes and in research projects a practical separation between the roles of organising the programme and of implementing the educational activities. This separation necessitates a strategic coordination to ensure alignment and effective delivery of planned activities. Quality control measures are essential in both contexts to maintain high standards and continuously monitor progress. Research projects are evaluated (quality control) and need to follow certain standards of quality set by associated educational institutions (compliance).

Both research projects and educational programmes are meant to deliver an impact beyond the programme end. Strategies to promote the programme or project to attract and engage the audience or stakeholders, e.g., for adoption of developed training modules, are therefore vital for success. Evaluating the impact and effectiveness of the programme or project is necessary for long-term sustainability, enabling adjustments and revisions to meet changing needs and circumstances.

2) *Differences*: While educational programme management often involves a hierarchical organizational structure, this is not easily applicable to large research projects, which comprise numerous organizations and stakeholders. In research projects, the targeted competences are not entirely identifiable at the outset or by the programme management, as research results need to be translated into training activities during the project cycle based on the evolving project outcomes.

Assessment, an important aspect in educational programme management, is typically not directly applicable in research projects, especially when European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) credits are not involved. Moreover, there's a challenge in assessing tacit skills in research projects, which are difficult to measure directly. In educational

programmes there is usually continuity in the target audience, which enables competence build-up, but also requires curricula to be coordinated. In contrast, research project training audiences are not expected to attend any sequence of activities. Training activities associated with a research project often conclude with the project's lifecycle, making them relatively short-lived compared to educational programmes. Conversely, educational programmes aim for enduring impact and may involve more continuous and long-term engagement with the audience beyond specific projects.

These differences highlight the need for a nuanced approach in applying educational programme management principles to research projects.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

As outlined above, there are elements of programme management that pertain to educational efforts in research projects, and elements that differ fundamentally. This section outlines how key elements of programme management may be adopted and how the approach can be modified to suit for educational activity coordination in research projects.

The applicability of classical educational programme management for large research projects hinges on an hierarchical organisation with the possibility of setting authoritative directions on building competence and targeted learning outcomes from the outset, and implementation policies. In contrast, research projects are distributed and targeted learning outcomes are subject to development. However, it is possible to adopt programme management elements into an alternative system of bottom-up definition and discovery of required competence and learning outcomes. We propose an agile combination of parallel bottom-up and top-down processes for the creation of training activities and their alignment through an educational strategy.

The proposed approach (as shown in Fig. 1), involves an initial conception and a cyclic update of an educational strategy, which is informed through the structured reporting of bottom-up created training activities. The analogy of the

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the process for the educational programme management.

proposed approach to the elements of the conventional educational programme management is drawn within Fig. 1. The four steps involved are described in detail below.

Step 1: As a first step, the technical areas, scope and ambitions of the project are identified, in order to set a direction for the educational programme. The educational program leader in consultation with all the actors involved (e.g., the partners which will carry out the activities) defines the technical topic areas which will be covered within the educational activities and their prioritisation. Generally, those topics are determined by the scope of the research projects and should be aligned with the expertise of the partners and their expectations with respect to the knowledge areas. In order to define the topics, an internal survey with the actors involved can be performed and the respective results analysed to come up with a final list. Likewise, the target groups to which the activities are addressed as well as the validation tools are determined in consensus.

Step 2: In the second stage takes place the development of the training activities and their description. Additionally, forms can be designed and filled for each activity in order to describe the aspects such as learning objectives, activity description, attendance, and other aspects, referred to as the training activity plan. This allows the traceability of the educational programme and a quick access to the key details of each activity held.

Step 3: The first iteration and cyclic update are then informed through bottom-up reporting, the technical topic areas, means of delivery as well as the training objectives and intended learning outcomes are collected. The reporting is organised via a template, training activity report, that informs the developers of training activities about the methodology and the required information. It is also recommended to design questionnaires in which the participants of the activity evaluate their experience and knowledge acquired. The feedback will

support to the improvement of further educational activities by tackling weaknesses identified by the participants and will be addressed to both educators and learners.

Step 4: In the last stage is performed an overall analysis of the educational activities to draw conclusions on achievements and lesson learnt. For this purpose, statistical analysis can be carried out to quantify the number of activities performed at each topic area, percentage target groups reached, etc. Therefore, conclusions can be drawn together with the actors involved in the research project. With the collected information, the ongoing direction of the training programme can be monitored and mapped against the ambitions set out for the project. Due to the cyclic update, the project participants are informed on the progress with respect to the set project ambition. This feedback enables the possible re-focussing and creation of additional training activities (in area, activity type, and intended learning outcomes) to meet the project ambition.

IV. CASE STUDY: ERIGRID 2.0 EDUCATIONAL STRATEGY

This section presents the experience from application of the above described methodology to develop and implement an educational strategy for a research project. ERIGRID 2.0 aims to expand the research services and tools provided by leading European research infrastructures for the validation of smart energy systems considering a holistic and cyber-physical systems-based approach. The goal was to effectively develop, deliver and coordinate educational activities related to the project’s outcomes (and the overall framework), in order to minimise the time required to interpret the research developments into training material that address the evolving needs of the energy sector and enhance the skills of the workforce. The case study is realized as follows.

Step 1: This step involved setting a direction for the educational programme by defining the technical topic areas, validation method and target groups to be covered in the train-

Fig. 2. Analysis of topics and methods covered by ERIGRID 2.0 project’s training activities.

TABLE I
LIST OF TECHNICAL TOPIC AREAS, DEFINITIONS, WHERE NOT OTHERWISE REFERENCED, ARE FOUND IN [16]

Technical Topic Area	Abbrev.	Reference
Distributed Energy Resources	DER	[17]
Energy Storage Systems	ESS	[18]
Distribution Management Systems and Distribution Network Operation	DMS	
Ancillary Services by DG, Storage and Active Grid Assets	AnS	[19]
Frequency and Voltage stability	FVS	
Microgrids	Mic	[20]
Multi-energy/carrier systems/sector coupling	MESC	
Inverter Dominated Power Systems	Inv	
ICT in Smart Grids	ICT	[21]
Demand Response	DR	[22]
Aggregation and Flexibility Management	AFM	[23]
Energy Communities	EC	[24]
Digitalization of Energy Systems	Dig	
DC Power Systems	DC	
Energy Markets	EM	[25]
Other	Other	
Validation Methods	Abbrev.	Reference
Simulations (Monolithic)	Sim	
Co-simulation	CoSim	[26]
Control and Power Hardware-in-the-loop	C/P HIL	[27]
Distributed Real Time Simulation	DRTS	[28]
Coupling of multiple entities	CME	
Other	Other	

ing activities. ERIGrid 2.0 project defined a set of application areas in an effort of setting a mutual understanding of areas which are of interest in the project as reported in [29], which were further developed into concept profiles, as summarised in [30]. Drawing from these, the relevant technical topic areas to be covered by the educational activities were identified, which are listed in Table I. Next, partners expressed their preferences in terms of technical topic areas, validation methods and target audiences, based on their expertise as well as their preferable means of delivery.

Step 2: Once the technical topic areas, validation methods, target groups and means of delivery of relevance for each partner were specified, the partners proceeded to develop specific training activities related to those. Training activity plans were created and distributed, describing the training objectives, intended learning outcomes based on Blooms Taxonomy, activity descriptions, and other relevant aspects.

Step 3: The ERIGrid 2.0 project followed a cyclic reporting process where technical areas, delivery methods, training objectives, and intended learning outcomes were continuously monitored and reported, using activity report forms. Additionally, feedback from participants was collected, aiding in the improvement of future educational activities.

Step 4: The project conducted an initial analysis of the delivered and under preparation educational activities to draw a first set of conclusions on achievements and lessons learned, in the mid of the project. Statistical analysis was performed to quantify the activities performed/to be performed in each topic area and assess the reach to the target audience. This data was used to make informed decisions, assess the discrepancy between the initial target and the current status, assess the level

Fig. 3. Categorisation of Bloom levels in the topics and methods covered by ERIGrid 2.0 project's training activities.

of comprehension achieved, so far and use this information to provide directions for future developments and continuously improve the training programme.

In Fig. 2, the ambition of the partners at the beginning of the project, the activities that are already delivered and those that are in planing status are presented. It can be easily observed that DER, ICT, and Dig have been technical topic areas covered by most of training activities, whereas the topic Inv, DR, AFM and EM have not been addressed in any planned or executed activities yet. Fig. 3 provides a reflection on the intended learning outcomes of the project's training activities. More specifically, a view of the categorisation according to Bloom Levels with respect to the technical topics and validation methods and tools covered by the training activities of project is shown. The "Application" level is dominant in both topics and methods. Audience of different skills and background are targeted by the training activities of the project - with power system professionals, young researchers and PhD students being the most prominent - in order to expand and enhance the ERIGrid 2.0 project's impact. The target groups of the training activities of the project are presented in Fig. 4.

The ERIGrid 2.0 project effectively applied an adaptive educational programme management methodology, aligning with the proposed steps. The identification of technical areas and scope, development of training activities, continuous reporting and monitoring, and subsequent analysis for improvement all contributed to a successful educational strategy within the project. This case study showcases how adherence to

Fig. 4. Target groups of ERIGrid 2.0 project's training activities.

these steps can lead to a relevant impact, and continuously improving educational initiative within a research project.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The evolving energy landscape, marked by rapid technological advancements, necessitates a proactive approach in addressing the widening skills gap within the workforce. The challenges posed by this transition demand a rethinking of traditional educational paradigms. This paper highlights the critical role of educational programme management in research projects, emphasizing the need for adaptability and alignment with the dynamic nature of the energy sector. By incorporating a flexible and agile educational strategy that combines bottom-up and top-down approaches, research projects can systematically bridge the gap between evolving research outcomes and targeted learning objectives. This approach ensures that educational activities are well aligned with project goals, enhancing the relevance and impact of the knowledge disseminated.

The proposed methodology, as demonstrated through the ERIGrid 2.0 project case study, showcases the successful application of educational programme management principles within a research project context. The holistic consideration of technical topics, target audiences, and learning outcomes enables tailoring of training activities for their continued alignment with research outcomes, and holds the potential to address the evolving needs of the energy sector. By implementing this adaptable methodology, research projects can effectively translate research outputs into impactful training programs, fostering a culture of continuous learning and innovation.

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A.2 Templates for Activity Plan and Report

A.2.1 Activity Plan Template

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

<Title>

Overview

Hosting partner:

Co-organizing partners:

Planned date: E.g. Summer '99 (as specific as possible)

Type of Activity:

Contact: Name, email address of person(s) filling in this form

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here?

Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

Target group(s)

Which are the target groups meant to participate and benefit from this training activity? As specific as possible (e.g. utility, suppliers, technical staff, consultants, high-school students, general public, etc.)

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

As Training Objectives describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective. For "Workshops & Seminars" and "Panel Sessions" this section is optional.

This module intends to ...

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as "Intended Learning Objectives" – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom's revised taxonomy to describe the school's objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. e.g. Produce a coherent test description for a HIL experiment
2. ...

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Outline of Training Activity

Describe here the key components and learning activities comprising the training activity. A time schedule can be included here if available.

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organizers (NA3-Training_Activity_Report_Form)

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A.2.2 Activity Report Template

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report <Title>

Overview

Hosting partner:

Co-organizing partners:

Delivered date:

Type of Activity: *select one of:* Workshops or Seminars (including virtual interactive workshops); Training Schools (Fill-in the additional fields!); Tutorials (e.g. in context of a conference); Special sessions and Panel Sessions; Training of Professionals; Training of High School Students

Contact: Name, email address of person(s) filling in this form

Agenda and Schedule of the event

Provide the agenda and/or schedule of the event. (The schedule mostly applies to summer/winter schools and workshops)

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

Provide the list of participants.

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

Provide information about the educational event, description of each presented topic, whether it was related to an ERIGrid 2.0 workpackage, etc.

Achievements and learning outcomes

Describe the main achievements and outcomes of the event (e.g. the participants familiarized themselves with topic A, etc.)

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

Provide statistics (No. Registered persons, No. of Attended Persons, No. of Project External Persons).

- A. *Insert a picture of the event video on YouTube or any other public repository (e.g. Zenodo)*
- B. *Insert photos of the event*

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

In case a questionnaire was distributed to participants, please provide the results.

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A.3 Training Activity Plans and Reports

In the following pages, the activity plans and reports of the realised events are included. They describe the performed tasks in detail.

- Training Activity Plan and Report: Goals and challenges of the future electricity markets 55
- Training Activity Plan and Report: Open-source models for research Panel Session 61
- Training Activity Plan and Report: Advanced Lab Testing Methods 65
- Training Activity Plan and Report: Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems 70
- Training Activity Plan and Report: DigiSect23 75
- Training Activity Plan and Report: RI Automation Workshop 79
- Training Activity Plan and Report: DigiSect24 89
- Training Activity Plan and Report: Development, Management and Applications of Open-Source Smart Energy Systems Education 93
- Training Activity Plan and Report: CIRED24 Workshop 98
- Training Activity Plan and Report: Summer School 102
- Training Activity Plan and Report: Training Series-DigSES 115
- Training Activity Plan and Report: Engineering-Validating CPES 118
- Training Activity Plan: Winter School on Sector Coupling 122

A.3.1 Goals and challenges of the future electricity markets

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan Goals and challenges of the future electricity markets

Overview

Hosting partner: HEDNO (Christos Krasopoulos, Panagiotis Karafotis)

Co-organizing partners: N/A

Planned date (approximate): July 2023

Type of Activity: Training of Professionals

Contact: Panagiotis Karafotis (p.karafotis@deddie.gr)

Short Description

Encouraging the exchange of knowledge on new technical challenges related to smart distribution grids through the outcomes of ERIGrid 2.0 project, will be a massive tool for the energy transition, which requires thorough adaptation of the DSOs to the energy system of the future, in line with EU energy policy developments.

The proposed seminar will discuss the goals and the challenges of the future electricity markets, regarding the status of demand response, electromobility, storage, telemetering and power electronics in Greece.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

In a changing energy system, cities in Europe are facing challenging structural changes. They are progressively urged to be able to host smarter and sustainable advanced technologies to deliver electricity in a more intelligent and efficient way to their citizens. The Distribution System Operators (DSOs) play a key role in ensuring this task, by updating, improving and modernizing the electric grids they manage and making the use of electric power smarter and easier.

This seminar provides power experts with the possibility to broaden their knowledge horizons regarding the technological fields of demand response, electromobility, storage, telemetering and power electronics.

Target group(s)

The seminar will be addressed to power professionals.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

- Demonstrate the HEDNO's role as a moderator for ongoing and new legislative developments, particularly in the fields of demand response, electromobility, storage, telemetering and power electronics.

A participant who completed this seminar is able to:

1. be familiarised with the concept and benefits of demand response strategies.
2. be familiarised with the technical requirements for the recharging infrastructure of electric vehicles and the optimal integration of E-Mobility in the Distribution Network.
3. be familiarised with the new technological achievements in storage and batteries.
4. be familiarised with the benefits of using power electronics in Distribution Network.

Outline of Training Activity

The seminar comprises of:

- Technical expertise
- Policy & Regulation

Evaluation approach

The success of the training activity will be evaluated by obtaining feedback from the participants through the completion of an evaluation questionnaire.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report

Goals and challenges of the future electricity markets

Overview

Hosting partner: HEDNO (Christos Krasopoulos, Panagiotis Karafotis)

Co-organizing partners: N/A

Delivered date: 13/07/2023

Type of Activity: Training of Professionals

Contact: Panagiotis Karafotis (p.karafotis@deddie.gr)

Agenda and Schedule of the event

<i>Goals and challenges of the future electricity markets</i>	
HEDNO workshop/training activity in the framework of the ERIGrid 2.0 research project	
Thursday 13 July 2023	
8.45-9.00	Event attendance & introduction
9.00-10.00	Antonios Papavasiliou <i>Assistant Professor, School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, National Technical University of Athens</i> <i>Introduction to electricity markets: the example of Greece</i>
10.00-10.30	Panagiotis Kotsampopoulos <i>Researcher, Smart Rue, NTUA</i> <i>Energy communities, local energy markets and energy management tools</i>
10.30-11.00	Konstantinos Manganiotis <i>Director, Measurements Division, HEDNO</i> <i>Smart Grids and Remote Metering</i>
11.00-11.15	Coffee break
11.15-12.00	Georgios Stamoulis <i>Professor, Department of Informatics, Athens University of Economics and Business</i> <i>Demand response: from theory to practice</i>
12.00-12.30	Antonios Antonopoulos <i>Assistant Professor, School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, National Technical University of Athens</i> <i>Synthetic Inertia from Power Electronics in Networks with High RES Penetration</i>
12.30-13.00	Isidoros Cocos <i>Master R&D Engineer, Intracom Telecom</i> <i>Flexibility in optimal management of electricity distribution networks</i>
13.00-13.15	Lunch break
13.15-13.45	Irene Leonidaki <i>Director, Network Design & Development Division, HEDNO</i> <i>New challenges in Network design and planning</i>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

13.45-14.15	Fotios Gakis <i>Head of Department, RES and Storage Branch, HEDNO</i> <i>Storage Systems connected to the Network or User Facilities</i>
14.15-14.30	Coffee break
14.30-15.00	Antonios Kladas <i>Professor, School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, National Technical University of Athens</i> <i>Development prospects of electromobility and implications for the energy sector</i>
15.00-15.30	Evangelos Karfopoulos <i>Technical Manager, I-SENSE, NTUA</i> <i>The role of electric vehicles in future power grids: Opportunities and challenges</i>
15.30-16.00	Athanasios Zarogiannis <i>Electromobility Consultant, Ministry of Environment and Energy</i> <i>Electromobility market - the present and next steps based on national and European framework</i>

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

During this training activity, the following topics were presented:

- Introduction to **electricity markets**: the example of Greece
- **Energy communities**, local energy markets and energy management tools
- **Smart Grids and Remote Metering**
- **Demand response**: from theory to practice
- Synthetic Inertia from **Power Electronics** in Networks with High RES Penetration
- **Flexibility** in optimal management of electricity distribution networks
- New challenges in **Network design and planning**
- **Storage Systems** connected to the Network or User Facilities
- Development prospects of **electromobility** and implications for the energy sector
- The role of **electric vehicles** in future power grids: Opportunities and challenges
- **Electromobility market** - the present and next steps based on national and European framework

Achievements and learning outcomes

The participants of the event familiarized themselves with a wide variety of modern topics in electric power systems, including:

- ✓ Electricity markets
- ✓ Energy communities
- ✓ Smart grids
- ✓ Remote metering
- ✓ Demand response
- ✓ Power electronics
- ✓ Power flexibility
- ✓ Network design and planning
- ✓ Storage systems
- ✓ Electromobility

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Statistics of the event

The event was attended by approximately 80 people, the majority of whom were external project participants.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.2 Open-source models for research Panel Session

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Open-source models for research and training in smart energy systems

Overview

Hosting partner: ICCS-NTUA
 Co-organizing partners: AIT, JRC
 Planned date: 27-29/03/2023

Type of Activity: Panel Session in Conference

Contact: Alkistis Kontou (alkistiskont@gmail.com)

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

Modelling of power and energy systems has traditionally been a task of paramount importance, both for the research community and the industry, aiming to investigate the static and dynamic performance of those rather complicated networks. To standardize such procedures, multiple benchmark energy networks as well as methodologies for the holistic testing of energy systems have been proposed in the previous years, with many of them however corresponding to proprietary material, not available to the wider community, a fact especially significant for the training of young engineers too. This panel session aims to present recent advances in open-source models and methods for research and training in smart energy systems, particularly focusing on energy networks' models, the documentation of test cases to be performed on such networks, and their utilization in the educational sector.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here?
 Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

Freely available open-source materials and tools for training in smart energy systems are crucial as they provide a broad range of learners with the opportunity to develop and enhance their practical skills, fostering accessibility, collaboration, and innovation in the field. This panel session aims to promote and demonstrate recent advancements in open-source models and methods for research and training in smart energy systems based on ERIGrid 2.0 experience and other initiatives and paradigms.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

As Training Objectives describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective. For "Workshops & Seminars" and "Panel Sessions" this section is optional.

The objective of the panel session is to present and inform about available open-source documentation approaches, benchmark networks for hardware-in-the-loop and open source modeling tools. The attendees will be able to recall and memorise this information.

Outline of Training Activity

Describe here the key components and learning activities comprising the training activity. A time schedule can be included here if available.

- Open-source documentation of simulation test cases: The PreCISE approach (15 mins)
- Holistic open-source documentation of benchmark energy networks (15 mins)
- Benchmark network for hardware-in-the-loop simulation (15 mins)
- Open-source modelling advancing education in energy systems (15 mins)
- Discussions (20 mins) [All panelists and attendees]

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organizers (NA3-Training_Activity_Report_Form)

N/A

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report

Open-source models for research and training in smart energy systems

Overview

Hosting partner: ICCS-NTUA

Co-organizing partners: AIT, JRC

Delivered date: 28/03/2023

Type of Activity: Panel Session in Conference

Contact: Alkistis Kontou (alkistiskont@gmail.com)

Agenda and Schedule of the event

Duration: 1.5 hours

Panel Information

Panel Session Title: **Open-source models for research and training in smart energy systems**

Moderator: Alexandros Paspatis

Speakers: Alkistis Kontou, Panos Kotsampopoulos, Thomas Strasser and Evangelos Kotsakis

Program
Introduction to the panel session (10 mins) Alexandros Paspatis
Open-source documentation of simulation test cases: The PreCISE approach (15 mins) Edmind Widl (online)
Holistic open-source documentation of benchmark energy networks (15 mins) Evangelos Kotsakis
Benchmark network for hardware-in-the-loop simulation (15 mins) Panos Kotsampopoulos (online)
Open-source modelling advancing education in energy systems (15 mins) Alkistis Kontou
Discussions (20 mins) All panellists and attendees

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

N/A

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

Provide information about the educational event, description of each presented topic, whether it was related to an ERIGRID 2.0 workpackage, etc.

This panel session presented advances in open-source models, methodologies, and resources for research and education in smart energy systems, highlighting the importance of freely available tools and comprehensive documentation for enhancing practical skills, fostering collaboration, and driving innovation in power systems analysis. The session began with an introduction by Alexandros Paspatis, followed by presentations on the PreCISE approach for open-source documentation of simulation test cases by Edmind Widl (online), holistic open-source documentation of benchmark energy networks by Evangelos Kotsakis, a benchmark network for hardware-in-the-loop simulation by Panos Kotsampopoulos (online), and the role of open-source modeling in advancing education in energy systems by Alkistis Kontou. Collectively, these discussions emphasized the value of accessible and standardized resources in empowering a diverse community of researchers, educators, and industry professionals to advance the development of next-generation smart energy systems.

Achievements and learning outcomes

Describe the main achievements and outcomes of the event (e.g. the participants familiarized themselves with topic A, etc.)

The panel session highlighted key advancements in open-source models and methodologies for smart energy systems, emphasizing their impact on research, education, and innovation. Open-source initiatives like the PreCISE approach for simulation test cases and holistic documentation of benchmark networks were showcased, demonstrating their significance for both academia and industry. The session also highlighted the role of open-source modeling in enhancing hands-on training for young engineers, fostering practical skills development. Additionally, it promoted the need for standardized, accessible tools to encourage collaboration and equitable resource sharing while integrating advanced techniques, such as hardware-in-the-loop simulation, to support the energy transition.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

Provide statistics (No. Registered persons, No. of Attended Persons, No. of Project External Persons).

30-35 Attendees

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

In case a questionnaire was distributed to participants, please provide the results.

N/A

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.3 Advanced Lab Testing Methods

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan Advanced Laboratory Testing Methods for Modern Power Systems

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: DTU, VTT, UoS, and TU Dortmund

Planned date: 08.-10.05.2023

Type of Activity: Workshop (organized via the EES-UETP activity)

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at; Mihai Calin, mihai.calin@ait.ac.at

Short Description

Lab testing workshop about experiences on the European level related to power and energy systems. The event is linked with IEA-ISGAN/SIRFN and is organized by the TU Dortmund as part of the EES-UETP activity. The project-related presentation incl. an introduction and overview of the ERIGrid 2.0 validation, testing, and education services provided by the coordinator AIT to researchers and engineers from the power and energy systems domain.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The training is required to provide general information to researchers and engineers from the power and energy systems domain in the form of a presentation/tutorial.

Target group(s)

All ERIGrid 2.0 stakeholders (academia/research, industry, energy utilities, standardization, general public).

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to show the higher complexity of future energy systems in the form of scenarios with different penetration levels of renewables. It also introduces the necessity of system-level design and validation approaches based on simulations and laboratory testing as well as the combination of them in a hardware-in-the-loop manner.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Outline of Training Activity

The presentation covers the following topics:

- Engineering problems and needs in the domain of smart energy systems
- The ERIGrid 2.0 vision and approach
- Validation and testing approaches
- Selected validation examples

Evaluation approach

An evaluation of the contributions to the laboratory workshop is planned by the organization team in the form of an online questionnaire.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report

Advanced Laboratory Testing Methods for Modern Power Systems

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: DTU, VTT, UoS, and TU Dortmund

Delivered date: 08.-10.05.2023

Type of Activity: Workshop (organized via the EES-UETP activity)

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at; Mihai Calin, mihai.calin@ait.ac.at

Agenda and Schedule of the event

The following figure provides a high-level overview of the agenda of the workshop in Dortmund, Germany:

WORKSHOP

ADVANCED LABORATORY TESTING METHODS FOR MODERN POWER SYSTEMS

DATE
May 8th – 10th 2023

LOCATION
TU Dortmund University
Germany

AIIST • AIT • DTU • Fraunhofer IWES • Fraunhofer IEE • H&S Hard- & Software Technologies • Sandia National Labs • TU Dortmund • University of Strathclyde • VTT Finland

Electric Energy Systems University Enterprise Training Partnership

Schedule

MONDAY, 8TH MAY 2023

10:15 – 10:45
Registration

10:45 – 11:00
Opening Session

11:00 – 12:00 ☒
Advanced Laboratory Testing Methods Supporting Grid Transition at Pace • Mazheruddin Syed • University of Strathclyde

- Lunch break •

13:30 – 14:30 ⚡
Wireless 5G for Smart Grid Protection Communication • Petra Raussi • VTT Finland

14:30 – 15:30 🇺🇸
Cybersecurity and Protection of DERs • Javier Hernandez-Alvidrez • Sandia National Labs

- Coffee break •

16:00 – 17:00 🇩🇪
HIL Testing of Multi-MW Wind Turbines • Florian Hans • Fraunhofer IWES

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Schedule

TUESDAY, 9TH MAY 2023

- 09:00 – 10:00 🇩🇪 | HIL Testing of grid-following and forming inverters • Hiroshi Kikusato • AIST
- 10:00 – 11:00 🇩🇪 | Rapid inverter control prototyping system for comprehensive HIL testing • Tobias Erckrath • Fraunhofer IEE
- Coffee break •
- 11:30 – 12:30 🇩🇪 | Automated Testing of control cabinets and protection devices • Jan Arph • H&S Hard- and Software Technologies
- Lunch break •
- 13:30 – 15:30 🇩🇪 | PHIL Validation of hardware-independent control algorithms, Visit to HGÜ Testzentrum • Rajkumar Palaniappan • TU Dortmund
- Coffee break •
- 15:30 – 17:30 🇩🇪 | Technical Visit to the Smart Grid Technology Lab • Alfio Spina • TU Dortmund
- Evening 18:00
- Dinner •

Schedule

WEDNESDAY, 10TH MAY 2023

- 09:00 – 10:00 🇩🇪 | Challenges and learnings from advanced testing systems in H2020 ERIGrid project • Thomas Strasser, Calin Mihai • AIT
- 10:00 – 11:00 🇩🇪 | System testing for multi-domain energy systems: methodology, use cases and platforms • Kai Heussen • DTU
- Coffee break •
- 11:30 – 12:30 🇩🇪 | Case study of CHIL with geographically distributed power systems • Oliver Pohl – Oliver Gehrke • TU Dortmund, DTU*
- Lunch break •
- 13:30 – 15:00 🇩🇪 | Hands-on testing with real-time simulators, TU Dortmund
- 15:00 – 15:30 | Final discussion
- 15:30 – 16:00 | Test for ECTS credits

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

35 participants from academia and industry as well as 15 presenters/lecturers joined the workshop in Dortmund, Germany; due to GDPR regulations, the attendance list cannot be shared.

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

Advanced laboratory testing can provide various opportunities to accelerate the roll-out of innovative technology and concepts for modern power systems, and many theoretical and practical challenges need to be assessed. The main focus of this workshop is on advanced laboratory testing methods that are essential to ensure reliability, safety and proper system integration of innovative solutions and technologies for modern power systems applications. These include sophisticated testing approaches based on the combination of simulation and full-hardware testing, also known as the hardware-in-the-loop approach.

There is a need for further investigations to improve and standardize those testing methods. In this regard, this workshop serves as a meeting point between specialists from the industry, academy and research centers to exchange ideas on this specific field. Notably, this workshop will bring together experts around the world to discuss technology, solutions, and state-of-the-art and future trends in advanced laboratory testing.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Besides the theoretical knowledge, numerous real-life experiences and examples ranging from early-stage research to daily operations will be provided. To familiarize with these topics, laboratory tutorials will be performed at the Smart Grid Technology Lab and the Protection and Automation Lab of the TU Dortmund University, thus providing relevant hands-on experiences.

Achievements and learning outcomes

Various testing methodologies and approaches ranging from (geographically distributed) real-time simulation over hardware-in-the-loop simulations to hardware experiments have been presented. Further details can be found in the related slides via this [link](#).

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

35 participants from academia and industry as well as 15 presenters/lecturers joined the workshop in Dortmund, Germany.

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

An online questionnaire was distributed by the workshop organisers, the results are provided via this [link](#).

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.4 Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan Designing and Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: IEEE Systems, Man, and Cybernetics Society (SMC)

Planned date: 01.10.2023

Type of Activity: Tutorial (at IEEE SMC 2023 conference)

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at

Short Description

A driving force for the realization of a sustainable energy supply in Europe is the integration of distributed, renewable energy resources. Due to their stochastic generation behaviour, energy utilities and network operators are confronted with a more complex operation of the underlying power grids. Additionally, due to technological developments, partly controllable loads (energy storage systems, heat pumps, electric vehicle supply equipment, etc.), integration with other energy sources (i.e., hybrid grids), changing regulatory rules, and the market liberalization, the system's operation needs adaptation. Sophisticated design approaches together with proper operational concepts and intelligent automation provide the basis to turn the existing power system into an intelligent entity, a so-called smart grid. Nowadays, the digitalization of smart grids and smart energy systems (electricity, gas, heat, etc.) plays a dominant role and provides the basis for future innovations.

During the last two decades a growing number of various research, technology development, and innovation activities have already been carried out in this domain. A various number of demonstration projects have already shown the applicability of the proposed smart grid approaches. Also, the extension of the smart grid concept which focuses on electric energy to multi-domain energy – towards smart energy systems – has been carried out during the last years.

While reaping the benefits that come along with those intelligent behaviours, it is expected that the system-level testing will need to play a significantly larger role in the development and roll-out of future solutions and technologies. Validation approaches, concepts, and corresponding tools for smart grids and smart energy systems are still not mature enough for effective usage. A key element in this context is the human factor as well as educated professionals, engineers, and researchers understanding the needs and methods for complex smart grids and smart energy systems validation in a multi-domain and cyber-physical manner. This is partly lacking today.

In summarizing, the following research and development topics are not sufficiently covered:

- Domain-specific adaptations of previously developed abstract validation procedures and corresponding

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

- concepts, methods, and tools are required to address advanced applications (low-inertia grids, microgrids, hybrid grids, etc.),
- Common and well-understood reference scenarios, use cases, and test case profiles for smart energy systems need to be provided to power and energy systems engineers and researchers; also, proper validation benchmark criteria and key performance indicators, as well as interoperability measures for validating smart grids and smart energy systems, need to be developed, extended, and shared with engineers and researchers in Europe,
- Harmonization and standardization of multi-domain cyber-physical systems-based evaluation and testing procedures are necessary, and
- Well-educated professionals, engineers, and researchers understanding smart grid and smart energy systems configurations in a multi-domain and cyber-physical manner addressing the upcoming energy transition need to be educated and trained on a broad scale.

This tutorial aims to tackle the above-mentioned requirements by introducing validation methods and tools for validating smart energy systems which are currently being developed in ERIGrid 2.0.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

A driving force for the realization of a sustainable energy supply is the integration of renewable energy resources. Due to their stochastic generation behaviour, energy utilities are confronted with a more complex operation of the underlying power grids. Additionally, due to technological developments, controllable loads, integration with other energy sources, changing regulatory rules, and market liberalization, the system's operation needs adaptation. Proper operational concepts and intelligent automation provide the basis to turn the existing power system into an intelligent entity, a smart grid. While reaping the benefits that come along with those intelligent behaviours, it is expected that system-level developments and testing will play a significantly larger role in realizing future solutions and technologies. Proper validation approaches, concepts, and tools are partly missing until now.

This tutorial aims to tackle the above-mentioned requirements by introducing validation methods and tools for validating smart energy systems which are currently being developed in ERIGrid 2.0.

Target group(s)

All ERIGrid 2.0 stakeholders (academia/research, industry, energy utilities, standardization, general public).

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to show the higher complexity of future energy systems in the form of scenarios with different penetration levels of renewables. It also introduces the necessity of system-level design and validation approaches based on simulations and laboratory testing as well as the combination of them in a hardware-in-the-loop manner.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Outline of Training Activity

The tutorial covers the following topics:

- Introduction to smart energy systems
- The ERIGrid 2.0 vision and approach
- Validation and testing approaches
- Selected validation examples

Evaluation approach

No evaluation is foreseen.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report

Designing and Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: IEEE Systems, Man, and Cybernetics Society (SMC)

Delivered date: 01.10.2023

Type of Activity: Tutorial (at IEEE SMC 2023 conference)

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at

Agenda and Schedule of the event

The tutorial covered the following topics:

- Introduction to smart energy systems
- The ERIGrid 2.0 vision and approach
- Validation and testing approaches
- Methods and tools
- Selected validation examples
- Education tools for researchers and professionals

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

Around 10 participants joined the event; due to GDPR regulations, the attendance list cannot be shared.

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

This tutorial discussed and summarized the main needs and requirements as well as the status quo in research and development related to the designing and validating of cyber-physical energy systems. Also, validation examples and short demos have been presented. Also, training and educational material has been introduced. Finally, research trends and necessary future activities have been outlined as well.

Achievements and learning outcomes

This module showed the expected future energy systems' higher complexity in scenarios with different penetration levels of renewables. It also introduced the necessity of system-level design and validation approaches based on simulations and laboratory testing as well as the combination of them in a hardware-in-the-loop manner.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

The following information about the tutorial was made available by SMC:

- No. of registered persons: n/a
- No. of attendees: 10
- No. of project external persons: 10

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

No evaluation has been carried out.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.5 DigiSect23

ERIGRID 2.0 Training Activity Plan 2nd Expert Workshop on Design and Operation of Digitalized Sector-Coupled Energy Systems (DigiSect 2023)

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: OFFIS, KTH, TUHH

Planned date: 20-21.04.2023

Type of Activity: Workshop

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at; Edmund Widl, edmund.widl@ait.ac.at

Short Description

This is the second international expert workshop in digitalization and sector-coupling of energy systems, as a continuation of the previous event at TUHH in 2022.

The speakers include professors, leading university researchers, and experts from Europe's grid operators and energy industries.

Workshop contributions are attributed to the following thematic clusters:

- Cluster 1 – Automation and Digitalization Technologies: focus on digital technologies enabling sector coupling and sector integration, including artificial intelligence, digital twins, IoT and communication, cyber security, simulation, etc.
- Cluster 2 – System architecture and operation strategies: focus on applications and best practices for sector coupling and sector integration both on system and component levels, including pilot sites, energy communities, innovative technologies, markets & regulation, etc.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The aim of this workshop is to bring together experts from Europe to exchange insights, enhance international collaboration, discuss EU project applications, and create a roadmap on possible trends and research directions for operation, control and digitalization in sector-coupled energy systems and sector integration (power, heating, gas, e-mobility, as well as citizens).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Target group(s)

All ERIGRID 2.0 stakeholders (academia/research, industry, energy utilities, standardization, general public).

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to show the higher complexity of future energy systems with a focus on digitalisation.

Outline of Training Activity

The activity consists of different presentations related to the digitalisation of smart energy systems.

Evaluation approach

No evaluation is foreseen.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

ERIGRID 2.0 Training Activity Report

2nd Expert Workshop on Design and Operation of Digitalized Sector-Coupled Energy Systems (DigiSect 2023)

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT
 Co-organizing partners: OFFIS, KTH, TUHH
 Planned date: 20-21.04.2023

Type of Activity: Workshop

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at; Edmund Widl, edmund.widl@ait.ac.at

Agenda and Schedule of the event

The following figure provides a high-level overview of the agenda of the workshop in Vienna, Austria:

THURSDAY, APRIL 20TH, 2023

11:30 – 12:30	Lunch and registration	
12:30 – 12:40	Welcome / Introduction	
12:40 – 13:40	Keynote Prof. Astrid Niele (University of Oldenburg, Germany): Challenges in cyber-physical energy systems: Of agents and data	Download Slides
13:40 – 14:00	Break	
14:00 – 15:20	Joachim Keiz (IAE Intec): Combine district heating and wastewater treatment plants	Download Slides
	Alexander Dreher (Fraunhofer IEE): Unleashing Flexibility: Cornerstones to Harvesting Residential Energy Resources	Download Slides
	Kai Strunz (TU Berlin): Object-oriented Modeling of Multi-Energy Systems: Methodology and Application to Berlin-Adlershof	Download Slides
15:20 – 15:45	Peter Palensky (TU Delft): Migrating from Natural Gas to Wind and Hydrogen in the Netherlands	Download Slides
	Break	
	Milos Cvetkovic (TU Delft): Enabling flexibility in integrated energy systems	Download Slides
15:45 – 17:00	Qianwen Xu (KTH): Control of renewable energy-hydrogen-based energy systems for isolated and grid connected applications	Download Slides
	Christian Becker (TU Hamburg): Modelling and Optimal Operation of Intelligent Integrated Energy Systems	Download Slides
	Moiz Ahmed (DLR EV): Distribution Grid Operations Management	Download Slides
	Discussion & Brainstorming	

FRIDAY, APRIL 21ST, 2023

9:00 – 10:20	Philipp Linnartz (RWTH Aachen): Cyber Security Risks in Power System Operation	Download Slides
	Stephan Ferenc (University of Oldenburg): NFD4Energy - A digital Infrastructure for Interdisciplinary Energy-System Research	Download Slides
	Pooya Davari (Aalborg University): Power Electronics for P2X: Challenges and Opportunities	Download Slides
10:20 – 10:45	Break	
10:45 – 11:45	Keynote Michael Niederkofler (actL energy, Austria): Energy Communities as Aggregated Flexibilities - Opportunities and Challenges on the Way to Becoming Participants in Flexibility Markets	Download Slides
11:45 – 12:45	Lunch	
12:45 – 14:00	Michael Taylor (Cardiff University): Techno-economic assessment of bi-directional low temperature district heating and cooling networks	Download Slides
	Vedran Peric (TU Muenchen): PHIL Architecture for Integrated Thermal-Electric Grids	Download Slides
	Edmund Widl (AIT): DigitalEnergyTestbed - An Open Testbed Prototype for Integrated Energy Systems	Download Slides
14:00 – 14:30	Bastian Pfarrherr (Stromnetz Hamburg): Innovative Ansätze zur Sektorkopplung in den Hamburger Energienetzen	Download Slides
	Wrap-up and Closing	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

Around 30 participants from academia and industry joined the event; due to GDPR regulations, the attendance list cannot be shared.

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

This is the second international expert workshop in digitalization and sector-coupling of energy systems, as a continuation of the previous event at TUHH in 2022.

The speakers include professors, leading university researchers, and experts from Europe's grid operators and energy industries.

Workshop contributions are attributed to the following thematic clusters:

- Cluster 1 – Automation and Digitalization Technologies: focus on digital technologies enabling sector coupling and sector integration, including artificial intelligence, digital twins, IoT and communication, cyber security, simulation, etc.
- Cluster 2 – System architecture and operation strategies: focus on applications and best practices for sector coupling and sector integration both on system and component levels, including pilot sites, energy communities, innovative technologies, markets & regulation, etc.

Achievements and learning outcomes

This module showed the higher complexity of future energy systems with a focus on digitalisation.

Further details can be found in the related slides via this [link](#).

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

Around 30 participants from academia and industry joined the event.

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

No evaluation has been carried out.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.6 RI Automation Workshop

ERIGRID 2.0 Training Activity Plan Research Infrastructure Automation Workshop 2024

Overview

Hosting partner: DTU (Risø Campus)

Co-organizing partners: AIT, RSE, TUD

Planned date: 24th and 25th September '24 (conjunction with ERIGRID 2.0 GA at DTU)

Type of Activity: Workshop

Contact: Kai Heussen, kheu@dtu.dk

Short Description

DTU will host a 2 half-day workshop aiming to showcase both ERIGRID2 achievements, but also invite a broader community to discuss how the community can contribute to “Accelerating the Energy Transition through Collaboration, Automation and Coupling of Research Infrastructures”.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

1. Dissemination of JRA4 demonstration outcomes
2. Engagement of the RI automation community for wider impact
3. Initiation of future activities

Target group(s)

technical staff, researchers, lab technology developers, research leaders.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

- Workshop -

Outline of Training Activity

The workshop will comprise three sessions with presentations, live lab demonstrations and time for discussions. The session topics will be:

1. *Collaboration*: metadata and digital tools for facilitating research collaboration and data exchange
 - Energy data platforms, Research data description and FAIR and/or open data aspects
 - Dataspaces for Energy Research – Technology, maturity, and use cases

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

- Test description for interpretability – toward FAIR experiments

2. *Automation*: how energy system test setups can be repeatable and reproducible (and less complex to handle)

- Repeatable and reproducible complex experiments , Configuration management
- Automated test setup generation
- Testing automation (e.g. OPENSVP - <https://github.com/sunspec/svp>)

3. *Coupling of Test Facilities*: Methods, Techniques and Technologies to couple large scale test resources from multiple RIs

- uAPI for research infrastructure interoperability
- Remote and sector coupling experiments incl. GDRTS
- GD-PHIL improvements concerning - Stability (ICCS)

Evaluation approach

The participants' experience will be evaluated through direct conversations with participants and a wrap-up and feedback session during the workshop. No formal evaluation is planned.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report

Research Infrastructure Automation

Workshop 2024

Overview

Hosting partner: DTU (Risø Campus)
 Co-organizing partners: AIT, RSE, TUD
 Planned date: 24th and 25th September '24 (conjunction with ERIGrid 2.0 GA at DTU)
 Type of Activity: Workshop
 Contact: Kai Heussen, kheu@dtu.dk

Agenda and Schedule of the event

13:00 - 13:20 Workshop opening

Session 1: Collaboration: metadata and digital tools for facilitating research collaboration and data exchange

Session Chair: Kai Heussen, DTU

- 13:20 - 13:40** Oliver Werth, OFFIS Towards a National Research Data Infrastructure for Interdisciplinary Energy System Research (NFDI4Energy)
- 13:40 - 14:00** Jawad Kazmi, AIT Dataspaces for Research – Technology, maturity, use cases
- 14:00 - 14:20** Artjoms Obusevs, ZHAW Overview of IEEE working group on big data and analytics
- 14:20 - 14:40** Sebastian Dupraz, BRGM Digital Twins Interoperability: challenge and perspectives
- 14:40 - 15:00** Q&A

Session 2: Automation: how energy system test setups become can repeatable and reproducible (and less complex to handle)

Session Chair: Jirapa Kamsamrong, OFFIS

- 15:20 - 15:40** Kourosh Malek, FZ Jülich The role of ontology and data management in cloud-connected automated labs
- 15:40 - 16:00** Ammar Malik and Terence O'Donnell, University College Dublin Automated Testing of Distributed Energy Resources (DER) : Use of an open source testing platform (OpenSVP) for testing smart inverters against European network connection standards EN50549 and VDE 4105
- 16:00 - 16:20** Filip Prössl, AIT Automated Test Setup Generation for Validating Smart Grids Software Ecosystems
- 16:20 - 16:40** Santiago Sanchez, SINTEF Cyber-physical metropolitan area digital substations test bench for evaluating intrusion detection systems
- 16:40 - 17:00** Q&A

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Laboratory tour & demo

17:00 - 18:20	Lab Tour	Refreshment and Initiation of laboratory tour	Risø Campus - Building 319
18:20 - 18:40	Oliver Gehrke, <i>DTU</i> Andres Acosta, <i>RWTH</i>	Global Configuration management for multi-site experiments	
18:40 - 19:00	Day 1 wrap-up	Configuration Management Demo	
19:00	Dinner	Dinner served in the laboratory facilities	Risø Campus - Building 310

Research Infrastructure Automation Workshop

Day 1: 24.09.2024	from 13:00 until 19:00	Place: DTU-Risø - B112
Day 2: 25.09.2024	from 09:00 until 14:00	Place : DTU-Risø - B319

Day 2

Session 3: Coupling of Testing Facilities: Methods, Techniques and Technologies to couple large scale test resources from multiple RIs

Session Chair 1: Panos Kotsampopoulos, NTUA
Session Chair 2: Thomas Strasser, AIT

09:00 - 09:20	Vetrivel Subramaniam, <i>TU Delft</i> and Andres Acosta, <i>RWTH Aachen</i>	Towards simplified and standardized experiments combining multiple research infrastructures: The ERIGRID 2.0 Universal API approach
09:20 - 09:40	Giuseppe Silano, <i>RSE</i>	Integrating Power-to-Heat Services in Geographically Distributed Multi-Energy Systems
09:40 - 10:00	Tesfaye Amare Zerihun, <i>SINTEF</i> and Oliver Gehrke, <i>DTU</i>	Laboratory Validation of Event-driven Co-simulation
10:00 - 10:20	Q&A	
12:00 - 13:00	Networking lunch	
13:00 - 13:30		Heat system demo final results
13:30 - 14:00	Day 2 Wrap-up	

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

In total, 59 participants signed up to join the event:

Alexandra Bach (RWTH), Alkistis Kontou (ICCS-NTUA), Ammar Malik (University College Dublin), Anthony Fraisse (DTU Wind and Energy Systems), Carsten Krüger (OFFIS e.V.), Evangelos Kotsakis (JRC), Filip Prösl Andrén (AIT Austrian Institute of Technology), Giuseppe Silano (Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico (RSE)), Gunter Arnold (Fraunhofer IEE), Ibrahim Abdulhadi (University of Strathclyde), Emilio Rodriguez (TECNALIA), Jirapa Kamsamrong (OFFIS e.V.), Kourosh Malek (Forschungszentrum Juelich GmbH), Kari Maki (VTT), Katja Sirviö (VTT), Kai Heussen (DTU Wind and Energy Systems), Panos Kotsampopoulos (ICCS-NTUA), Kristian Sevdari (DTU Wind and Energy Systems), Leon Aahave Uhd (DTU Wind and Energy Systems), Luca Barbierato (Politecnico di Torino), Marcus Bär (Helmholtz Berlin), Mayank Garg (OPAL RT Germany), Mohammad Arhum (OFFIS e. V.), Nils Müller (DTU Wind and Energy Systems), Artjoms Obusevs (ZHAW), Oliver Gehrke

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

The on-site participation was at about 40-50 participants at any point in time, since some didn't show up to the event and a few only participated in only one of the days.

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

The workshop topic centred on various issues relevant for advancing smart energy research infrastructures, with a focus on acceleration and digitalization opportunities. The workshop content was defined by the three main session themes:

1. *Collaboration*: metadata and digital tools for facilitating research collaboration and data exchange
2. *Automation*: how energy system test setups can be repeatable and reproducible (and less complex to handle)
3. *Coupling of Test Facilities*: Methods, Techniques and Technologies to couple large scale test resources from multiple RIs

The event was organized in these main sessions, with additional lab tours and a dinner in the SYSLAB facilities. This frame gave ample opportunity for participants to engage and interact with another.

The workshop was co-organized with the RISEnergy and NEST projects and the IEA-ISGAN-SIRFN network, but the organization was firmly anchored in ERIGRID 2.0.

Speakers were invited and facilitated by the co-organizing partners: RISEnergy participants (Sebastian Dupraz, BRGM/ECCSEL, Kourosh Malek, FZJ), with some overlapping participation from RISEnergy/ ERIGRID 2.0 – e.g. from AIT, NTUA and DTU). A number of presentations were included and facilitated by the ISGAN-SIRFN network. The workshop included an open discussion on how the community assembled at the workshop may carry on, e.g. through projects like RISEnergy, and a 2025 instance of the workshop was anticipated by several participants

All presentations slides have been made publicly available via Zenodo:

Heussen, K., & Gehrke, O. (2024). Research Infrastructure Automation Workshop 2024 (2.0). Research Infrastructure Automation Workshop 2024, Roskilde, Denmark. The ERIGRID 2.0 Consortium. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14699238>

Achievements and learning outcomes

The workshop achieved to create a new topic-setting event, with a potential of creating and maintaining a research community beyond the ERIGRID 2.0 project scope. In that respect, the most motivating outcome of the event was that a participant volunteered host of "the RI Automation Workshop 2025". Several participants approached the organizers, congratulating for a well-organized and successful workshop. Apart from the inspired presentations and the productive panel

discussions, a concrete outcome from the workshop were the discussions hosted in the wrap-up session. Participants agreed that several of the presented concepts and open software ideas were worth to follow up on at a community level. For example, the scaling & reproducibility enhancing tools “uAPI”, “Configuration Management” and “Kubernetes-netem” as well as the “OpenSVP” platform were shortlisted as specific tools with sufficient community backing to follow beyond the project ERIGRID 2.0 scope.

The discussion notes have been included in the file [“Wrap-up Session Notes.pdf”](#) as part of the [ZENODO release](#).

Pictures from the event

Presentations

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Panel discussions

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Group

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Lab Tour & Dinner

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.7 DigiSect24

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

3rd Expert Workshop on Design and Operation of Digitalized Sector-Coupled Energy Systems (DigiSect 2024)

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: OFFIS, KTH, TUHH

Planned date: 16-17.05.2024

Type of Activity: Workshop

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at; Edmund Widl, edmund.widl@ait.ac.at

Short Description

This is the third international expert workshop in digitalization and sector-coupling of energy systems, as a continuation of the previous two events, including the 1st workshop at TUHH in 2022 and the 2nd in 2023.

The speakers include professors, leading university researchers, and experts from Europe's grid operators and energy industries.

Workshop contributions are attributed to the following thematic clusters:

- Cluster 1 – Automation and Digitalization Technologies: focus on digital technologies enabling sector coupling and sector integration, including artificial intelligence, digital twins, IoT and communication, cyber security, simulation, etc.
- Cluster 2 – System architecture and operation strategies: focus on applications and best practices for sector coupling and sector integration both on system and component levels, including pilot sites, energy communities, innovative technologies, markets & regulation, etc.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The aim of this workshop is to bring together experts from Europe to exchange insights, enhance international collaboration, discuss EU project applications, and create a roadmap on possible trends and research directions for operation, control and digitalization in sector-coupled energy systems and sector integration (power, heating, gas, e-mobility, as well as citizens).

Target group(s)

All ERIGrid 2.0 stakeholders (academia/research, industry, energy utilities, standardization, general public).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to show the higher complexity of future energy systems with a focus on digitalisation.

Outline of Training Activity

The activity consists of different presentations related to the digitalisation of smart energy systems.

Evaluation approach

No evaluation is foreseen.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

ERIGRID 2.0 Training Activity Report

3rd Expert Workshop on Design and Operation of Digitalized Sector-Coupled Energy Systems (DigiSect 2024)

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: OFFIS, KTH, TUHH

Planned date: 16-17.05.2024

Type of Activity: Workshop

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at; Edmund Widl, edmund.widl@ait.ac.at

Agenda and Schedule of the event

The following figure provides a high-level overview of the agenda of the workshop in Stockholm, Sweden:

3rd Expert Workshop on Design and Operation of Digitalized Sector-Coupled Energy Systems

Overview

The aim of the workshop is to bring together experts from Europe to exchange insights and to create a roadmap on possible trends and research directions for operation, control and digitalization in sector-coupled energy systems and sector integration.

Workshop contributions are attributed to the following thematic clusters:

- Cluster 1 – **Automation and Digitalization Technologies**: focus on digital technologies enabling sector coupling and sector integration, including artificial intelligence, digital twins, IoT and communication, cyber security, simulation, etc.
- Cluster 2 – **System architecture and operation strategies**: focus on applications and best practices for sector coupling and sector integration both on system and component levels, including pilot sites, energy communities, innovative technologies, markets & regulation, etc.

Event link: [3rd Expert Workshop on Design and Operation of Digitalized Sector-Coupled Energy Systems \(DigiSect 2024\) on 16-17 May](#)

Agenda

Thursday, May 16th, 2024 (11:00-18:15)

11:00 Registration opens at Digital Futures
 11:00-11:30 Registration at Digital Futures Hub
 11:30 – 12:30 Lunch at Syster o Bror restaurant
 12:30 – 12:40 Welcome / Introduction Qianwen Xu (KTH)
 12:40 – 13:40 Keynote
 Ambra Sannino (VP, Vattenfall) "Digitalization – a key enabler of the energy transition"
 13:40 – 14:00 Break

14:00 – 15:20 **Session 1 – Cluster 1: Smart energy** – 4 Presentations & Panel Discussion
 Antonello Monti (RWTH Aachen) "Smart Data for Smart Energy"
 Antonia Kung (Triolog) "Integrating cross-cutting standards with vertical standards"
 Danica Kraljicic (Svenska kraftnat) "How CIM and data exchange is used for European Energy collaboration"
 Wout van Veenendaal (NV Nederlandse Gasunie) "Molecules in an Electron World – an intersectoral approach"

Our Sponsors:
 Digital Futures Dig-IT Lab KTH Energy Platform & KTH Digitalization Platform
 IEEE PES & PELS Sweden IEEE PES Chapter Austria H2020 ERIGRID 2.0

Friday, May 17th, 2024 (9:00-15:30)

9:00 – 10:00 **Session 3 – Cluster 1: Digitalization** – 4 Presentations & Panel Discussion
 Andreas Ullig (RWTH Aachen) "Digitalization in Electric Distribution Grids – Technological Trends, Opportunities and Challenges"
 Christof Wittwer (Fraunhofer ISE) "Digital system integration for the transformation of the energy system"
 Mark Stefan (AIT) "Grid-friendly energy communities in PARMENIDES"
 Md Tanbir Hossain (Hitachi Energy) "Leveraging digitalization to support energy transition: Hitachi Energy Perspective"

10:20 – 10:45 Break
 10:45 – 11:45 **Panel about education for Digitalized sector coupled energy systems**
 Moderator: Judith Neube, Professor, OFFIS
 Panelists: Dimitris Lagos (NTUA), Arnold Pears (KTH), Lars Nordström (KTH), Christian Becker (TUHH)

11:45 – 12:45 Lunch

12:45 – 14:00 **Session 4 – Cluster 2: Flexibility** – 4 Presentations & Panel Discussion
 Andreas Raul, Professor, Carl von Ossietzky "Digital Twins for Battery Cell Production and Their Possible Interfaces with Battery Management Strategies"
 Iver Bakken Sperstad (SINTEF) "Classifying and characterizing power system flexibility solutions"
 Janas Arund Vogel, (KTH Dig-IT Lab) "Industrialising digitalisation for the built environment"
 Alexandre Canal (Cardiff) "Flexibility from the residential heat sector"

14:15 – 15:15 **Discussion & Brainstorming**
 15:15 – 15:30 **Wrap-up and Closing** Lars Nordström (KTH)

Our Sponsors:
 Digital Futures Dig-IT Lab KTH Energy Platform & KTH Digitalization Platform
 IEEE PES & PELS Sweden IEEE PES Chapter Austria H2020 ERIGRID 2.0

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

Around 50 participants from academia and industry joined the event; due to GDPR regulations, the attendance list cannot be shared.

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

This is the third international expert workshop in digitalization and sector-coupling of energy systems, as a continuation of the previous two events, including the 1st workshop at TUHH in 2022 and the 2nd in 2023.

The speakers include professors, leading university researchers, and experts from Europe’s grid operators and energy industries.

Workshop contributions are attributed to the following thematic clusters:

- Cluster 1 – Automation and Digitalization Technologies: focus on digital technologies enabling sector coupling and sector integration, including artificial intelligence, digital twins, IoT and communication, cyber security, simulation, etc.
- Cluster 2 – System architecture and operation strategies: focus on applications and best practices for sector coupling and sector integration both on system and component levels, including pilot sites, energy communities, innovative technologies, markets & regulation, etc.

Achievements and learning outcomes

This module showed the higher complexity of future energy systems with a focus on digitalisation.

Further details can be found in the related slides via this [link](#).

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

Around 50 participants from academia and industry joined the event.

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

No evaluation has been carried out.

A.3.8 Development, Management and Applications of Open-Source Smart Energy Systems Education

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Development, Management and Applications of Open-Source Smart Energy Systems Education

Overview

Hosting partner: ICCS-NTUA

Co-organizing partners: UCY

Planned date: 3-5/9/2024

Type of Activity: Panel Session in Conference

Contact: Alkistis Kontou (alkistiskont@gmail.com)

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

ICT technologies and interdisciplinary background are of paramount importance for a deep understanding of the evolving smart energy systems. Therefore, proactive response from academia, industry stakeholders and the wider community is essential, to rapidly adapt teaching methodologies and effectively train the next generation of engineering professionals, as well as current professionals who need to stay updated with emerging technologies. Open-source tools and accessible educational materials can significantly enhance the education of individuals studying or working in this sector. This panel session aims to present innovative, hands-on educational methods that enhance comprehension and skill advancement for students, researchers, and professionals. Examples and opportunities will be showcased for providing free access to tools, services, and infrastructures. Additionally, a methodology for establishing an educational strategy to deliver open-source educational content during the lifespan of research projects will be presented. This can foster a culture of continuous and innovative learning, bridging the gap between academia and industry.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here?

Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

The aim of this panel session is to promote and inform potential users of the available free access possibilities to advanced laboratory infrastructure in Europe. Moreover, the participants will be informed about open-source highly configurable hardware converters that can be used for teaching and

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

training purposes. Concluding, the ERIGRID 2.0 developed methodology for development and management of open-source educational material in research projects is presented to promote replicability and support the development and organization of open-source educational material in the frame of research projects

Target group(s)

Which are the target groups meant to participate and benefit from this training activity? As specific as possible (e.g. utility, suppliers, technical staff, consultants, high-school students, general public, etc.)

Professionals in the field of smart energy systems, students, and researchers in the field of smart energy systems.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

As Training Objectives describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective. For "Workshops & Seminars" and "Panel Sessions" this section is optional.

This panel session aims to present advanced laboratory testing methods and promote free access possibilities in Europe. Moreover, presents how open-source educational material can be developed and managed within the frame of research projects.

The attendees will be able to recall and relate this information.

Outline of Training Activity

Describe here the key components and learning activities comprising the training activity. A time schedule can be included here if available.

- Simulation and PHIL based Smart Energy Systems Education using Open-Source "Laboratory" and "Real Life Laboratory" environment (15 min)
- Smart Energy Systems: Modern open-source learning management systems for real-time supervision and control (15 min)
- OwnTech: a fully open-source technology suite for microgrid fast prototyping, simulation and teaching (15 min)
- Methodology for Development and Management of Open-Source Educational Material in Research Projects (15 min)
- Discussions (15 mins)

All panelists and attendees

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organizers (NA3-Training_Activity_Report_Form)

N/A

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report

Development, Management and Applications of Open-Source Smart Energy Systems Education

Overview

Hosting partner: ICCS-NTUA

Co-organizing partners: UCY

Delivered date: 9/2024

Type of Activity: Panel Session in Conference

Contact: Alkistis Kontou (ICCS-NTUA)

Agenda and Schedule of the event

Provide the agenda and/or schedule of the event. (The schedule mostly applies to summer/winter schools and workshops)

There was a change in relation to initial planning due to the last minute unavailability of one of the panellists.

09:00 - 10:10 Panel Session "Development, Management and Applications of Open-Source Smart Energy Systems Education" (Session Chair: Alkistis Kontou)

ICT technologies and interdisciplinary knowledge are crucial for understanding smart energy systems. A proactive approach from academia, industry, and the community is needed to adapt teaching methods and train the next generation of engineers. Open-source tools and educational materials can enhance learning for those in this sector. This panel session will present innovative educational methods for students, researchers, and professionals, showcasing examples and opportunities for free access to tools and services. A strategy for delivering open-source educational content during research projects will also be presented, fostering continuous learning and bridging the gap between academia and industry.

- *Rad Stanev (TUS), "Simulation and PHIL based Smart Energy Systems Education using Open-Source "Laboratory" and "Real Life Laboratory" environment"*
- *George Makrides (UCY), "Smart Energy Systems: Modern open-source learning management systems for real-time supervision and control"*
- *Veit Hagenmeyer (KIT), "Experiences with the open source tools PROOF, pyWatts and eASIMOV at KIT"*
- *Alkistis Kontou (ICCS-NTUA), "Methodology for Development and Management of Open-Source Educational Material in Research Projects"*

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

N/A

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

Provide information about the educational event, description of each presented topic, whether it was related to an ERIGRID 2.0 workpackage, etc.

This panel session explored innovative educational approaches for smart energy systems using open-source tools and resources. Rad Stanev (TUS) presented the application of simulation and Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL) techniques in both "laboratory" and "real-life laboratory" environments to enhance smart energy education. George Makrides (UCY) discussed modern open-source learning management systems for real-time supervision and control of smart energy systems. Veit Hagemeyer (KIT) shared experiences with open-source tools, including PROOF, pyWatts, and eASIMOV, used at KIT. Lastly, Alkistis Kontou (ICCS-NTUA) introduced a methodology for developing and managing open-source educational materials within research projects, as an effective way to disseminate and transfer the output knowledge to students and professionals.

Achievements and learning outcomes

Describe the main achievements and outcomes of the event (e.g. the participants familiarized themselves with topic A, etc.)

The panel session on "Development, Management, and Applications of Open-Source Smart Energy Systems Education" achieved valuable insights into advancing smart energy systems education through open-source tools. Presentations demonstrated practical applications of simulation and Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL) environments for hands-on learning, highlighted the use of open-source platforms for real-time system supervision and control, and shared experiences with advanced tools like PROOF, pyWatts, and eASIMOV for data analysis and modeling. Moreover, the methodology developed in the frame of ERIGRID 2.0 for developing and managing open-source educational content within research projects was presented along with lessons learned from its application. Overall, the session promoted the development and use of open-source resources to foster continuous learning and enhance interdisciplinary expertise in smart energy systems.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

Provide statistics (No. Registered persons, No. of Attended Persons, No. of Project External Persons).

Approx. 30 attendees.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

In case a questionnaire was distributed to participants, please provide the results.

N/A

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.9 CIRED24 Workshop

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Qualification and Validation of Grid Services from the grid-forming inverters of Hybrid and Renewable Energy Plants

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: KEMA, UoS, IEE, DERlab, IEA ISGAN/SIRFN, CIRED 2024 Vienna Workshop

Planned date: 20.06.2024

Type of Activity: Workshop

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at; Erik de Jong, erik.dejong@kema.com

Short Description

This workshop will look into the role of in particular the grid-forming inverters that are providing grid services from hybrid and renewable energy plants, their prevailing and upcoming requirements and future possibilities. Speakers from industry will highlight the trends and real-life challenges experienced today and emphasize the urgent need for future, reliable deployment of such services.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

A key aspect to bestow confidence in the application will be the qualification and validation of these services and the associated equipment on a system level. This workshop will cover how these validation requirements translate into the testing of the actual equipment within a system context. ERIGrid2 experts and researchers will present their findings and ongoing research in this area. There will also be a unique opportunity to witness how such testing is performed in an advanced research and testing laboratory as well as network with colleagues on this emerging topic.

Target group(s)

All ERIGrid 2.0 stakeholders (academia/research, industry, energy utilities, standardization, general public).

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to show the higher complexity of future power grids with grid services from grid-forming inverters.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Outline of Training Activity

The activity consists of different presentations related to the qualification and validation of grid services from grid-forming inverters.

Evaluation approach

No evaluation is foreseen.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report

Qualification and Validation of Grid Services from the grid-forming inverters of Hybrid and Renewable Energy Plants

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: KEMA, UoS, IEE, DERlab, IEA ISGAN/SIRFN, CIRED 2024 Vienna Workshop

Planned date: 20.06.2024

Type of Activity: Workshop

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at; Erik de Jong, erik.dejong@kema.com

Agenda and Schedule of the event

The following figure provides a high-level overview of the agenda of the workshop in Vienna, Austria:

Workshop on Qualification and Validation of Grid Services from grid-forming inverters of Hybrid and Renewable Energy Plants
20 June 2024, Vienna, Austria

12:00 – 13:00 Shuttle transfer from Austria Center Vienna & Registration (light lunch served)

Session "Registration, Opening, and Welcome"

13:00 – 13:30 Opening & Welcome by Thomas Strasser (AIT)

Technical Session 1 "Grid-forming inverters in the power landscape" (Erik de Jong (KEMA))

13:30 – 13:50 „Grid Control 2.0 - Control and Stability of Inverter Dominated Power Systems“ by Gunter Arnold (Fraunhofer IEE)

13:50 – 14:10 „Grid Forming Converter Deployment in the UK: Developments, Challenges and Opportunities“ by Misher Syed (WSP)

14:10 – 14:30 „Supporting Distributed Restart: Experiences with PHL Testing of Grid Forming Converters with Black Start Capability“ by Zhenqiang Feng (University of Strathclyde)

Lab tour & Networking during coffee break

14:30 – 15:30 AIT Power System/Smart Grid Lab Tour and Group Photo

15:30 – 16:00 Coffee break & Networking

Technical Session 2 "Testing requirements for GFFs, now & in the future"(Christos Krasopoulos (HEDNO))

16:00 – 16:20 „Experimental validation of grid-forming VSGs with enhanced synchronization stability margin“ by Francisco Jesus Matas Diaz (University of Sevilla)

16:20 – 16:40 "Challenges of the inertial response validation and testing for the grid-forming power converters" by Andres Tarraso (UPC/AIT) | Zoran Miletić (AIT)

16:40 – 17:00 „Testing GFI at Fraunhofer IEE“ by Gunter Arnold (Fraunhofer IEE)

Session "Closing"

17:00 – 17:30 Closing remarks by Thomas Strasser (AIT)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Workshop on Qualification and Validation of Grid Services from grid-forming inverters of Hybrid and Renewable Energy Plants
20 June 2024, Vienna, Austria

Arrival and Meeting Location

The ERIGrid 2.0 Technical Workshop will take place at the Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT):
AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH
TECHbase (Room GG2_F4_M1A, 4th floor, follow the signs)
Giefinggasse 2
1210 Vienna, Austria
Phone number: +43 564 8251135 (Elisabeth Mirakotsky)

Shuttle transport from Austria Center Vienna to AIT will be available for registered participants.
The shuttle will depart from the main entrance of Austria Center Vienna, Level -1 at 12:00 sharp.

Virtual Meeting Information

The workshop will not be streamed, nor recorded. Participation will be in person.

Meeting Registration

All attendees are requested to register for this workshop at the following ERIGrid2 project website:
<https://erigrd2.eu/register-now-for-the-erigrd-2-0-workshop-at-ciired-2024/>.

The ERIGrid2 workshop is free of charge and a registration for the CIRED'24 event is **not** required.

Social event

Registered participants are invited by the ERIGrid 2.0 project to a dinner on the day of the workshop.
The dinner will be held at Restaurant **Lugeck**, located at Lugeck 4, 1010 Vienna.
The dinner starts at 19:30. There will be no shuttle transfer back to or from the Austria Center Vienna for the social event.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

Around 25 participants from academia and industry joined the event; due to GDPR regulations, the attendance list cannot be shared.

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

This workshop will look into the role of in particular the grid-forming inverters that are providing grid services from hybrid and renewable energy plants, their prevailing and upcoming requirements and future possibilities. Speakers from the industry will highlight the trends and real-life challenges experienced today and emphasize the urgent need for future, reliable deployment of such services. The speakers include leading researchers from academia and industry.

Achievements and learning outcomes

This module showed approaches and experiences from the qualification and validation of grid services from grid-forming inverters of hybrid and renewable energy plants.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

Around 25 participants from academia and industry joined the event.

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

No evaluation has been carried out.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.10 Summer School

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Advanced operation and control of active distribution networks: 2nd Edition

Overview

Hosting partner: ICCS-NTUA, HEDNO

Co-organizing partners: DERlab, TUD, UCY

Planned date: Summer 2024

Type of Activity: Training School

Contact: Alkistis Kontou (alkistiskont@gmail.com)

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

Distribution networks have a key role in the transformation of the energy system, characterised by the massive integration of distributed generation, storage and electric vehicles, adoption of ICT solutions and consumer engagement. The ERIGrid 2.0 Summer School aims to address those topics, highlighting the role of Hardware in the Loop (HIL) simulation as an efficient tool for developing and testing smart control strategies. The programme includes lectures on key aspects of modern distribution networks and smart grids, such as:

- Microgrids, smart grids and hierarchical control
- Power system resilience assessment and enhancement
- Advanced protection schemes
- Decentralized control and blockchain
- Digitalization of power systems
- Cybersecurity of active distribution networks
- Provision of flexibility, demand response and energy markets
- Electric Mobility
- Machine learning, block chain and forecasting models

The participants will have a unique chance to attend:

- Attend lectures from presenters from distinguished universities. The topics are related to s
- Participate in dedicated laboratory sessions where advanced Controller HIL (CHIL) and Power HIL (PHIL) experiments will take place

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

- Pay a visit to the Meltemi smart grid pilot site (awarded by the Smart Grids European Technology Platform) at a seaside location a few kilometers from Athens
- Attend an industry session with the Greek distribution network operator HEDNO, including discussions with industry experts and visits to real installations

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here? Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

The summer school aims to address ERIGRID 2.0 relevant topics on smart grids and integrated systems, specifically on control & ancillary services of DERs, digitalization of power systems and efficient, flexible & resilient operation of power systems.

Target group(s)

Which are the target groups meant to participate and benefit from this training activity? As specific as possible (e.g. utility, suppliers, technical staff, consultants, high-school students, general public, etc.)

Undergraduate & PhD students, young researchers and professionals.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

As Training Objectives describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective. For "Workshops & Seminars" and "Panel Sessions" this section is optional.

The Summer School intends to:

- Introduce the participants to topics relevant to smart energy systems
- Involve and expose the participants to advanced laboratory testing methods, concepts and procedures
- Promote practical exposure to network operation, interactive learning from experts, networking and career and research inspiration
- Present the example of a living lab (Meltemi camp site) built on a real residential camp site

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as "Intended Learning Objectives" – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom's revised taxonomy to describe the school's objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

A student who completed this course is able to:

- Recall complex concepts on topics related to control & ancillary services of DERs, digitalization of power systems and efficient, flexible & resilient operation of power systems
- Analyze the testing procedure of Industrial Power Plant Controllers for RES applications
- Apply CHIL tests of inverter controls

Outline of Training Activity

Describe here the key components and learning activities comprising the training activity. A time schedule can be included here if available.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

	1 st Day	2 nd Day	3 rd Day	4 th Day
Topics	<i>Control & Ancillary Services of DERs</i>	<i>Digitalization of power systems</i>		<i>Efficient, flexible & resilient operation of power systems</i>
10:00 - 14:30	Lectures, including one coffee break & lunch	Lectures, including one coffee break & lunch	<i>Industry Session with HEDNO</i>	Lectures, including one coffee break & lunch
14:30-16:30	Lab Session 1	Lab Session 2		Visit to Meltemi

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organizers (NA3-Training_Activity_Report_Form)

A questionnaire will be distributed to the participants.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report

Advanced operation and control of active distribution networks: 2nd Edition

Overview

Hosting partner: ICCS-NTUA, HEDNO

Co-organizing partners: DERlab, TUD, UCY

Delivered date: 3-6/6/2024

Type of Activity: Training School

Contact: Alkistis Kontou (alkistiskont@gmail.com)

Agenda and Schedule of the event

Provide the agenda and/or schedule of the event. (The schedule mostly applies to summer/winter schools and workshops)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Agenda

	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday
Topics	<i>Control & Ancillary Services of DERs</i>	<i>Digitalization of power systems</i>	<i>Industry Session with HEDNO</i>	<i>Efficient, flexible & resilient operation of power systems</i>
10:00-10:10	Welcome and Introduction Prof. Nikos Hatziaargyriou (NTUA)	Towards the digitalized centralized protection for modern power systems applying 5G Prof. Mazaher Karimi (University of Vaasa)	Visit to HEDNO SCADA DMS	Decentralized control and blockchain Prof. Iasonas Kouveliotis-Lysikatos (University of Peloponnese)
10:10-10:45	Microgrids as building blocks of smart grids Prof. Nikos Hatziaargyriou (NTUA)			
10:45-11:30	Microgrid primary and secondary control Dr. Dimitris Lagos (NTUA)	Recent deep learning advances to energy forecasting Dr. George Sideratos (NTUA)	Visit to HEDNO Laboratories of Electricity Meters and Measurement Transformers	Leveraging flexibility in smart distribution networks Dr. Angelina Syrri (NTUA)
11:30-11:45	Coffee Break	Coffee Break		Coffee Break
11:45-12:30	Advanced laboratory testing of active distribution networks Dr. Panos Kotsampopoulos & Alkistis Kontou (NTUA)	Cybersecurity of active distributions networks Prof. Charalambos Konstantinou (KAUST)		Presentations of the HEDNO laboratories and telemetering sections
12:30-13:15	Advanced ancillary services from PV & Storage Units Dr. George Makrides (FOSS)	Cybersecurity of load-frequency control of smart energy systems Andrew D. Syrmakesis (NTUA)	Power system resilience assessment and enhancement Ektoras Stasinios (NTUA)	
13:15-14:30	Lunch Break	Lunch Break	Discussion with HEDNO Experts	Visit to Meltemi camp pilot site
14:30-16:30	Lab session: HIL Testing of industrial Power Plant Controller for RES applications (PROTASIS S.A.)	Lab session: 1. Cybersecurity of digital substations Vetrivel S. Rajkumar (TUDelft) 2. CHIL tests of inverter controls (NTUA)		

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Day 3 (Wednesday 05.06.2024): Industry Session, HEDNO

A. Agenda

Time	Description	Site
10:00-10:15	Arrival ON YOUR OWN to 1 st site: 3is Septemvriou 111, 10434, Athens	1st Site
10:15-11:15	Visit to: Attica's Distribution Network Control Center <i>Topic: Network Operation - SCADA - DMS</i>	
11:15-12:00	Break and transport by HEDNO bus to 2 nd site: Agias Annis 70, 12241, Athens	2nd Site
12:00-12:30	<i>Coffee Break</i>	
12:30-13:30	HEDNO Experts Session <u>A. Presentations</u> 1. Konstantinos Kalatzis , Head of Laboratories and Radio Sector: <i>"Presentation of HEDNO Laboratories: Smart Meter Laboratory, Electricity Theft Detection Laboratory, Measurement Transformers Laboratory, Instruments Calibration Laboratory, and Radio Communications Laboratory"</i> . 2. Theodoros Boumis , Head of Telemetry Operations Sector: <i>"Advanced Metering Infrastructures"</i> .	
	<u>B. Discussion</u> Questions, Exchange of thoughts between Ph.D. Students, Researchers and HEDNO Engineers.	
13.30-14.30	Tour at HEDNO Laboratories of Electricity Meters and Measurement Transformers	
14.30-15.00	Break and transport by HEDNO bus to Metro Station "Syntagma"	

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

There is a signed list of participants but it is not provided here for GDPR purposes.

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

Provide information about the educational event, description of each presented topic, whether it was related to an ERIGRID 2.0 workpackage, etc.

On June 3rd-6th 2024 the ERIGRID 2.0 Summer School on Advanced Operation and Control of Active Distribution Networks, 2nd Edition took place at the premises of the National Technical University Athens (ICCS-NTUA) and the Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator (HEDNO).

The first and second day of the ERIGRID 2.0 Summer School consisted of lectures and HIL lab sessions at School of Electrical and Computer Engineering – NTUA, including industrial experiences. The lectures covered a range of topics, including microgrids and their role as building blocks in smart grids, primary and secondary control in microgrids, advanced laboratory testing for active distribution networks, and ancillary services provided by PV and storage units. Additional sessions

focused on digitalized centralized protection using 5G technology, the application of deep learning in energy forecasting, and cybersecurity considerations for active distribution networks and load-frequency control in smart energy systems. The Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) laboratory sessions focused on practical experiences, including industrial testing of power plant controllers for renewable energy systems (RES), cybersecurity of digital substations, and hands-on testing of inverter controls. Participants were divided into four groups to engage in these interactive, hands-on experiences.

On the third day, participants visited selected installations of the Greek DSO, HEDNO, starting with a tour of Attica's Distribution Network Control Center, where they learned about network operation, SCADA, and DMS systems. This was followed by an expert session led by HEDNO professionals, focusing on various aspects of the organization's operations. The day continued with a tour of the HEDNO Laboratories for Electricity Meters and Measurement Transformers.

On the fourth day, the focus shifted to lectures covering several key topics, including decentralized control and blockchain applications in power systems, leveraging flexibility in smart distribution networks, the integration of electric mobility into power systems, and strategies for assessing and enhancing power system resilience. The day ended with a visit to the Meltemi Camp pilot site, followed by social activities.

Achievements and learning outcomes

Describe the main achievements and outcomes of the event (e.g. the participants familiarized themselves with topic A, etc.)

The school provided PhD students and young researchers with a mixture of lectures, practical laboratory sessions, industry sessions and visits to modern installations. Specifically, the attendees learned about:

- Microgrids, smart grids and hierarchical control
- Advanced laboratory testing methods, with emphasis on Hardware-in-the-Loop
- Digitalization of power systems
- Cybersecurity of active distribution networks
- Provision of flexibility and demand response
- Integration of electric mobility in power systems
- Machine learning, block chain and forecasting models
- Power system resilience

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

Provide statistics (No. Registered persons, No. of Attended Persons, No. of Project External Persons).

- A. Registered persons: 56
- B. Participants: 24

Photos

DAY 1

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

DAY 2

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

DAY 3

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

DAY 3

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

The results of the questionnaire will be presented in the deliverable "D-NA3.3 Lessons Learned and Recommendations for Laboratory Education and E-learning Tools".

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.11 Training Series-DigSES

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan Online Training Series on the Digitalisation of Smart Energy Systems

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: IMP (coordinator of the linked H2020 SINERGY project)

Planned date: 19.-22.02.2024

Type of Activity: Online training lecture (webinar style)

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at; Filip Prössl Andrén, filip.proestl-andren@ait.ac.at

Short Description

Together with the linked Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Framework Program (H2020) SINERGY project and the ERA-Net Smart Energy Systems RESili8 a virtual training course on the digitalisation of smart energy systems is planned.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The training is required to provide general information about the digitalisation of smart energy systems to engineers and researchers who are active in the power and energy system.

Target group(s)

All ERIGrid 2.0 stakeholders (academia/research, industry, energy utilities, standardization, general public).

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

The objectives are related to the digitalisation of power and energy systems; details will be worked out during the next few months.

Outline of Training Activity

The training school will be offered virtually with interactive lectures. Details about the concrete structure of the training school will be worked out during the next few months.

Evaluation approach

An evaluation of the contributions to online training school is planned by the organization team.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report

Online Training Series on the Digitalisation of Smart Energy Systems

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: IMP (coordinator of the linked H2020 SINERGY project)

Planned date: 19.-22.02.2024

Type of Activity: Online training lecture (webinar style)

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at

Agenda and Schedule of the event

Targeting students, young professionals, as well as researchers, the training event is split into the following four parts:

- Lecture 1, Monday, February 19, 2024, 14:00-16:00 CET, "Modelling and simulation of integrated energy systems", E. Widl (AIT Austrian Institute of Technology)
- Lecture 2, Tuesday, February 20, 2024, 14:00-16:00 CET, "Integrated Energy Services, Cyber Security Issues, and Analytical Services", V. Janev, V. Timcenko, S. Rakas, D. Jelic (Institute Mihajlo Pupin)
- Lecture 3, Wednesday, February 21, 2024, 14:00-16:00 CET, "Designing and Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems", F. Prössl Andrén, T. Strasser (AIT Austrian Institute of Technology)
- Lecture 4, Thursday, February 22, 2024, 14:00-16:00 CET, "Cyber-Physical Tests Beds for Validation of Large-Scale Smart Grid Apps", C. Gavriluta, D. Vettoretti (AIT Austrian Institute of Technology)

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

Around 240 registrations and 120 participants (details see [02 AIT Online Training Series](#))

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

Together with the linked Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Framework Program (H2020) SINERGY project and the ERA-Net Smart Energy Systems RESili8 a virtual training course on the digitalisation of smart energy systems is planned.

Achievements and learning outcomes

The training material (presentations and recordings) is provided at [02 AIT Online Training Series](#).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

Around 240 registrations and 120 participants (details see [02 AIT Online Training Series](#))

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

An online questionnaire was distributed by the training organisers, the results are provided at [02 AIT Online Training Series](#).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.12 Engineering-Validating CPES

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Approaches, Methods, and Tools for the Engineering and Validation of Cyber-Physical Energy Systems

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: IEEE Systems, Man, and Cybernetics Society (SMC)

Planned date: 06.10.2024

Type of Activity: Tutorial (at IEEE SMC 2024 conference)

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at

Short Description

During the last two decades, a growing number of various research, technology development, and innovation activities have already been carried out in this domain. Various demonstration projects have already shown the applicability of the proposed smart grid approaches. Also, the extension of the smart grid concept which focuses on electric energy to multi-domain energy – towards smart energy systems – has been carried out during the last years.

While reaping the benefits that come along with those intelligent behaviors, it is expected that system-level design and testing will need to play a significantly larger role in the development and roll-out of future solutions and technologies. Design and validation approaches, concepts, and corresponding tools for smart grids and smart energy systems (also referred to as cyber-physical energy systems) are still not mature enough for effective usage. A key element in this context is the human factor as well as educated professionals, engineers, and researchers understanding the needs and methods for complex smart grids and smart energy systems validation in a multi-domain and cyber-physical manner. This is partly lacking today.

In summary, the following research and development topics are not sufficiently covered:

- Domain-specific adaptations of previously developed abstract design and validation procedures and corresponding concepts, methods, and tools are required to address advanced applications (low-inertia grids, microgrids, hybrid grids, etc.),
- Common and well-understood reference scenarios, use cases, and test case profiles for cyber-physical energy systems need to be provided to power and energy systems engineers and researchers; also, proper validation benchmark criteria and key performance indicators, as well as interoperability measures for validating cyber-physical energy systems, need to be developed, extended, and shared with engineers and researchers in Europe,

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

- Harmonization and standardization of multi-domain cyber-physical systems-based evaluation and testing procedures are necessary, and
- Well-educated professionals, engineers, and researchers understand cyber-physical energy systems configurations in a multi-domain and cyber-physical manner addressing the upcoming energy transition need to be educated and trained on a broad scale.

This tutorial aims to tackle the above-mentioned requirements by introducing proper methods and tools for designing and validating cyber-physical energy systems which are currently being developed in the European project ERIGrid 2.0 as well as the Austrian project PowerTeams.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

A driving force for the realization of a sustainable energy supply is the integration of renewable energy resources. Due to their stochastic generation behaviour, energy utilities are confronted with a more complex operation of the underlying power grids. Additionally, due to technological developments, controllable loads, integration with other energy sources, changing regulatory rules, and market liberalization, the system's operation needs adaptation. Proper operational concepts and intelligent automation provide the basis to turn the existing power system into an intelligent entity, a smart grid. While reaping the benefits that come along with those intelligent behaviours, it is expected that system-level developments and testing will play a significantly larger role in realizing future solutions and technologies. Proper validation approaches, concepts, and tools have been partly missing until now.

This tutorial aims to tackle the above-mentioned requirements by introducing validation methods and tools for validating smart grids and energy systems.

Target group(s)

All ERIGrid 2.0 stakeholders (academia/research, industry, energy utilities, standardization, general public).

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to show the higher complexity of future energy systems in the form of scenarios with different penetration levels of renewables. It also introduces the necessity of system-level design and validation approaches based on simulations and laboratory testing as well as the combination of them in a hardware-in-the-loop manner.

Outline of Training Activity

The tutorial covers the following topics:

- Introduction to smart energy systems
- The ERIGrid 2.0 vision and approach
- Validation and testing approaches
- Selected validation examples

Evaluation approach

No evaluation is foreseen.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report

Approaches, Methods, and Tools for the Engineering and Validation of Cyber-Physical Energy Systems

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: IEEE Systems, Man, and Cybernetics Society (SMC)

Delivered date: 06.10.2024

Type of Activity: Tutorial (at IEEE SMC 2024 conference)

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at

Agenda and Schedule of the event

The tutorial covered the following topics:

- Higher complexity in cyber-physical energy systems
- Engineering problems, needs, and research trends
- Approaches for design and engineering
- Methods for test preparation
- Integrated design, validation, and team collaboration

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

Around 6 participants joined the event; due to GDPR regulations, the attendance list cannot be shared.

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

This tutorial discussed and summarized the main needs and requirements as well as the status quo in research and development related to the designing and validating of cyber-physical energy systems. Also, validation examples and short demos have been presented. Also, training and educational material has been introduced. Finally, research trends and necessary future activities have been outlined as well.

Achievements and learning outcomes

This module showed the expected future energy systems' higher complexity in scenarios with different penetration levels of renewables. It also introduced the necessity of system-level design and validation approaches.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

The following information about the tutorial was made available by SMC:

- No. of registered persons: n/a
- No. of attendees: 6
- No. of project external persons: 6

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

No evaluation has been carried out.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.13 Winter School on Sector Coupling

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Sector coupling for Electricity and District Energy Systems

Overview

Hosting partner: DTU

Co-organizing partners: AIT, TUD, OFFIS

Planned date: 10-14th March 2025

Type of Activity: Training School

Contact: Kai Heussen, kheu@dtu.dk

Short Description

An affordable and fully renewable energy supply can be facilitated through further integration of all energy sectors. Ideally, flexibility resources could flow across several sectors, balancing and coordinating consumption, transport and energy conversion across the full energy infrastructure. To actualize the objective advantages of integrated energy systems, such coordination would require to overcome technical, academic, regulatory and financial barriers.

This winter school will introduce fundamental principles of several energy sectors and showcase several potential solutions and research challenges in sector coupling. The course offers hands-on training in research methods, live laboratory experiments and simulation tools to investigate sector coupling across electricity and district heat networks. The course is hosted in the SYSLAB Multi-energy facility of DTU and includes visits to sector coupling field sites in the region of Copenhagen.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Being familiar with one sector, we wonder: what are the dynamics, constraints and operating objectives in other sectors? Which are the relevant actors, what are the financial and technical limitations? Are there examples of how these barriers can be overcome? And how can we simulate, implement and test solutions that incorporate multiple sectors?

ERIGrid 2.0 is committed to facilitating research, development and especially experimental work on Sector Coupling, that is in the intersection between smart grids, district heating and flexible industrial processes. The concept of this winter school is to bring together lecturers from different fields in order to train the next generation of researchers in the challenges that each field has to overcome. The cross-disciplinary setting is chosen to place emphasis on the need to address cross-sectoral challenges, aiming to overcome disciplinary boundaries – because problems and future solutions are more likely to be found in such collaboration.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Target group(s)

Early-stage researchers, especially PhD students.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. Motivate sector coupling applications of with relevant use cases and examples
2. Explain operational principles of electricity and heat networks, and the technologies that link several sectors, as, e.g., e-mobility power-to-gas, and heat pumps.
3. Identify practical and research challenges for sector coupling and how these relate to established practices
4. Describe, execute and tune a simulation model of a co-simulation district heating system,
5. Design and evaluate a sector coupling experiment executed in a physical lab.

Outline of Training Activity

Date	Topic	Time
10.3.2025	Multi-domain Energy Systems – Introduction & State of the Art	12:00 – 18:00
11.3.2025	Sector Coupling – Technologies, Use Cases & Research Challenges	09:00 – 18:00
12.3.2025	Live District Energy Lab Session & Excursion to Sector Coupling Sites	09:00 – 18:00
13.3.2025	Operational Sector Coupling Analysis Tools and Methods	09:00 – 18:00
14.3.2025	Hands-on Analysis of Laboratory Measurements and Simulation Results	09:00 – 13:00

Evaluation approach

The activity will be evaluated by a set of surveys to inform organisers and teachers about the learning experience and quality of the training. For students, a formative evaluation is planned during the activity and for those that require ECTS points, an examination is made possible by the end of the activity.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Appendix B: Staff Exchange Activity Reports

In the following pages, the activity reports of the realised staff exchanges are included. They describe the performed tasks in detail.

B.1 Activity Report 1 - JRA3.3 – Configuration Management

European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition

Project Acronym: **ERIGrid 2.0**

Project Number: **870620**

Staff Exchange Summary Report

JRA3.3 – Configuration Management

Stay Period: 31/07/2023 to 03/08/2023

Funding Instrument: Research and Innovation Action
Call: H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1
Call Topic: INFRAIA-01-2018-2019 Integrating Activities for Advanced Communities

Project Start: 1 April 2020
Project Duration: 54 months

Visiting Researchers: Oliver Gehrke (DTU), Andres Costa (RWTH), Arhum Mohammad (OFFIS)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Report Information

Document Administrative Information	
Project Acronym:	ERIGrid 2.0
Project Number:	870620
Staff Exchange Name:	JRA3.3 – Configuration Management
Document Identifier:	ERIGrid2-Report-Staff-Exchange-JRA3_config
Report Version:	v2.0
Report Submission Date:	2023-11-20
Keywords:	Configuration, European Union (EU), H2020, Project, ERIGrid 2.0, GA 870620
Status:	Final

Change Log

Date	Version	Author/Editor	Summary of Changes Made
09/11/2023	v1.0	Vetrivel (TUD)	Draft report template
20/11/2023	V2.0	Vetrivel (TUD)	Final version

1 Staff Exchange Overview

1.1 Researcher and Host Information

Staff Exchange Information	
Staff Exchange Name	JRA3.3 – Configuration Management
Visiting Researcher Home Orgs.	RWTH, DTU, and OFFIS
Visiting Researchers Name	Oliver Gehrke (DTU), Andres Costa (RWTH), Arhum Mohammad (OFFIS)
Host Organisation	TUD
Stay Period	31/07/2023 to 03/08/2023

1.2 Motivation and Purpose

The JRA3 staff exchange centered on the software development of the configuration management approach, proposed in JRA 2.3. It broadly consists of two components:

1. An offline global configuration/description of data flows between the participating RIs.
2. An online automated mapping of local RI signals to data channels for the experiment, based on the global description.

The staff exchange developed the above mentioned aspects with a simple proof-of-concept to demonstrate the results. This served as tangible outcomes of JRA3.3/3.4.

2 Main Outcomes and Lessons Learned

2.1 Results

The main objective of the staff exchange was to further build upon and develop automation for the global experiment configuration file and concept, originally drafted in JRA2.3.

Following were the key achievements/results achieved:

1. Development of python scripts to read global configuration and produce local configuration files to automate multi-RI experiments and thereby improve reproducibility.
2. Testing of the configuration management approach with a simple Proof-of-Concept (PoC) using a specific transport.

It is foreseen that the results of the staff-exchange will be further developed and used within the scope of the JRA4 demonstrations.

A dedicated github repository contains all the code and is currently still under development. It will be made publicly available via the ERIGrid 2 github page once ready.

2.2 Lessons Learned

The major takeaways/lessons learned from the staff exchange were as follows:

- Software testing and coding is more efficient in smaller groups.
- In-person interactions helped to save time in subsequent coding exercises.

3 Conclusions

The JRA3.3 staff exchange was highly useful in speeding up the software development and prototyping process. Furthermore, the developed scripts and configuration files are planned to be use within the ongoing demonstrations in JRA4 for improved reproducibility and experimental automation. In summary, the staff exchange was successful in fostering greater collaborations and advancing task progress within JRA3 and ERIGrid 2.

Appendix A. Photo from Staff Exchange

Figure 1 Staff-exchange group photo. Researchers from left to right: TUD, DTU, RWTH, and OFFIS.

Consortium

Disclaimer

All information provided reflects the status of the ERIGrid 2.0 project at the time of writing and may be subject to change.

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B.2 Activity Report 2 - High-fidelity PHIL testing

European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition

Project Acronym: **ERIGrid 2.0**

Project Number: **870620**

Staff Exchange Summary Report

High-fidelity PHIL testing

Stay Period: 01/07/2024 to 09/07/2024

Funding Instrument: Research and Innovation Action
Call: H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1
Call Topic: INFRAIA-01-2018-2019 Integrating Activities for Advanced Communities

Project Start: 1 April 2020
Project Duration: 54 months

Visiting Researchers: Katja Sirviö and Ville Ollikainen (VTT)

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Report Information

Document Administrative Information	
Project Acronym:	ERIGrid 2.0
Project Number:	870620
Staff Exchange Name:	High-fidelity PHIL testing
Document Identifier:	ERIGrid2-Report-Staff-Exchange-StaffExchangeName-draft-vn.n
Report Version:	v1.2
Report Submission Date:	08/08/2024
Keywords:	Laboratory testing, Hardware-In-the-Loop, European Union (EU), H2020, Project, ERIGrid 2.0, GA 870620
Status:	draft

Change Log

Date	Version	Author/Editor	Summary of Changes Made
12/07/2024	v1.0	Katja Sirviö (VTT)	Draft report
12/07/2024	V1.1	Alkistis Kontou (ICCS-NTUA)	Review
13/07/2024	v1.2	Katja Sirviö (VTT)	Draft
08/08/2024	V1.2	Ville Ollikainen (VTT)	Review & Final

1 Staff Exchange Overview

1.1 Researcher and Host Information

Staff Exchange Information	
Staff Exchange Name	High-fidelity PHIL testing
Visiting Researcher Home Org.	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland
Visiting Researcher Name	Katja Sirviö and Ville Ollikainen
Host Organisation	ICCS-NTUA
Stay Period	01/07/2024 to 09/07/2024

1.2 Motivation and Purpose

The primary motivation for this staff exchange between ICCS and VTT was to share expertise in constructing Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL) test setups. The importance of this training is significant, as PHIL setups necessitate a power amplifier to interface power hardware with a digital real-time simulator, which can introduce additional dynamics, potentially leading to instability and inaccuracies. ICCS-NTUA has developed advanced interface algorithms that improve the stability and accuracy of PHIL setups, which VTT personnel need to master for effective coordination. Additionally, ICCS-NTUA aimed to receive feedback from the visiting researchers regarding the experiment and knowledge exchange. This training is aligned with WP11 – JRA2, focusing on "Improved and Extended Real-Time/Co-simulation and HIL Tools," and WP13 – JRA4, which deals with the "Integration and Demonstration of Services in the Extended Research Infrastructure."

This project aimed to create a comprehensive guide for designing a PHIL environment, emphasizing Power Interface (PI) stability, protection schemes, and the necessary development steps to achieve a stable and accurate simulation and testing setup. The PHIL studies and lab exercises covered various components, including the Ideal Transformer Method (VT-ITM), amplifier characteristics, digital-to-analogue and analogue-to-digital conversions, and the impact of time delays on system stability.

2 Main Outcomes and Lessons Learned

2.1 Results

The project began with a detailed study of the PHIL environment design based on (Ashrafidehkordi et al., 2023; Kotsampopoulos et al., 2012; Lauss et al., 2011; Lehfuss et al., 2012; Liu et al., 2021; Ren, 2007; Ren et al., 2008).

The design incorporates insights from the Ideal Transformer Method (VT-ITM). This method was used to model both the software (SW) and hardware (HW) parts of the system, focusing on accurate voltage transfer between simulated and real systems using controlled current and voltage sources. This setup allowed for precise voltage control through feedback loops and real-time adjustments.

A current filter was introduced in the feedback path to enhance stability in PHIL simulations. This significantly improved system stability, with proper parameterization crucial to maintaining a balance between stability and accuracy. Without this filter, the PHIL simulations would have been unstable, highlighting the importance of correct filtering techniques.

Amplifiers were categorized into linear and switching types. Linear amplifiers, operating in the transistor's linear region, provide high linearity and minimal distortion, making them suitable for high-fidelity applications. In contrast, switching amplifiers, which rapidly toggle transistors between on and off states, offer greater efficiency but require additional filtering to manage noise and distortion.

The development of the HIL setup included creating a Simulink model that represented an electrical circuit/power system with a VT-ITM type of PI. Stability analysis using Nyquist and Bode criteria demonstrated that system stability depended heavily on the resistance ratio R_{SW}/R_{HW} , with ratios equal to or greater than one indicating instability. A first-order low-pass (RC) filter was designed to stabilize the system, with its -3 dB cutoff frequency being a key characteristic for defining the filter's bandwidth and attenuation properties.

The PHIL simulations also considered the effect of time delay, which can introduce additional dynamics that affect system stability. Simulink and RSCAD models were adjusted to include time delay components, allowing for more accurate analysis and mitigation of these effects. Incorporating time delay into the models helped develop compensation strategies to ensure overall system stability despite inherent communication lags.

Following stability analysis in Simulink, an equivalent RSCAD model was developed. This model included comprehensive protection schemes to prevent uncontrolled voltage drops or current rises. Key protection schemes, such as over-current (OC) and over-voltage (OV) protections, were integrated into the RSCAD software to ensure safety and stability during PHIL experiments.

Figure 1: Software and hardware interaction in a PHIL setup.

2.2 Lessons Learned

Several important lessons emerged from this study. Firstly, implementing proper filtering techniques is critical for maintaining system stability. Incorrect filter parameterization can lead to instability, emphasizing the need for precise adjustment and testing.

Secondly, the choice between linear and switching amplifiers must be carefully considered based on application requirements. While linear amplifiers offer high fidelity, switching amplifiers provide efficiency, necessitating a trade-off based on specific needs.

Thirdly, stability analysis is crucial in developing a HIL setup. The resistance ratio R_{SW}/R_{HW} plays a significant role in system stability, and careful management of this ratio is essential to avoid instability.

Additionally, considering time delays is vital for accurate PHIL simulation. Time delays can significantly impact system behaviour, and compensating for these delays through appropriate modelling and control strategies is essential for maintaining stability.

Lastly, integrating comprehensive protection schemes is vital to safeguarding the PHIL system's software and hardware components. These schemes prevent potential damage from over-/undervoltage or overcurrent conditions, ensuring the overall safety and reliability of the testing environment.

3 Conclusions

The staff exchange successfully achieved its goal of sharing knowledge and training VTT personnel in constructing PHIL test setups. The study demonstrated the feasibility and importance of developing robust and stable systems for modern power testing. The Ideal Transformer Method (VT-ITM) effectively transferred voltage between simulated and real systems while proper filtering techniques ensured system stability. Incorporating the effects of time delay into PHIL simulations was critical for developing accurate and reliable models. This consideration enabled the creation of more robust control strategies, ensuring stability even with inherent communication lags.

The project highlighted the need to carefully consider amplifier types and their application-specific characteristics. Stability analysis using Nyquist and Bode criteria and the management of resistance ratios were crucial in developing a reliable HIL setup. Comprehensive protection schemes were successfully integrated, ensuring the safety of the PHIL environment.

These findings underscore the importance of detailed design and testing in developing advanced power systems, which will contribute to the resilience and efficiency of future energy infrastructures. Appendix A presents some photos from the stay.

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Appendix A. Photos

Figure 2. Developing PHIL: a) Modelling the SW and HW of the test system with RSCAD, b) Monitoring the voltage and current of the inverter in the loop in RSCAD.

Figure 3: Happy researchers after successful PHIL testing.

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